

D7.2 Data Management Plan (Second Version)

Deliverable information	
WP	WP 7 Project Coordination and Management
Document dissemination level	PU Public
Deliverable type	ORDP Open Research Data Pilot
Lead beneficiary	KNAW
Contributors	All partners
Document status	Final
Document version	V1.0
Date	28/10/2022
Authors	Andrea Scharnhorst (KNAW) Task lead Rene van Horik (KNAW) Enrico Daga (OU) Marilena Daquino (UNIBO) Elena Musumeci (MiC) Peter van Kranenburg (KNAW) Christophe Guillotel-Nothmann (CNRS-IREMus) Marco Gurrieri (CNRS-IREMus) Valentina Presutti (UNIBO) Marta Clementi (UNIBO) Albert Meroño Peñuela (KCL) Monica Turci (UNIBO) Eleonora Marzi (UNIBO) Antonio Puglisi (DP) Raphaël Fournier-S'niehotta (CNAM)
Reviewers	Elena Giglia (University of Turin), external reviewer Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra (DARIAH.EU) external reviewer Marjan Grootveld (DANS) internal review Marilena Daquino (UNIBO) internal review

INTENTIONALLY BLANK PAGE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004746

Project information

Project Start \ Date: 1st of January 2021

Project Duration: 40 months

Project website: <http://www.polifonia-project.eu>

Project contacts

Project Coordinator

Valentina Presutti

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
Department of Language, Literature and Modern Cultures (LILEC)

E-mail: valentina.presutti@unibo.it

Project Manager

Marta Clementi

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
Research division

E-mail: marta.clementi@unibo.it

POLIFONIA consortium

No.	Short name	Institution name	Country
1	UNIBO	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA	Italy
2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS SRL	Italy

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004746

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive summary

This second version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) follows the template structure for an Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) (section 2). As elaborated in the first version of the DMP (Admiraal et al. 2021), we see data management planning as inherent part of the overall knowledge exchange coordination in the project, and therefore closely related to the development of the socio-technical roadmap (Guillotet-Nothmann et al. 2022). In the first section *Introduction* we summarise Polifonia's approach towards data management planning. We further detail the progress made from the DMP version 1 to 2, and by which methods those were achieved.

In section 2 *Polifonia Data Management Plan*, we use the ORDP template, to document the achievements of data management in Polifonia, and discuss main achievements of Polifonia such as the Polifonia Ecosystem, the Polifonia Knowledge Graph, and Polifonia Ontology and the Polifonia Portal from the point of view of best practices in data management.

A short *Outlook* section summarises tasks and steps toward the DMP version 3.

Document history

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) -Institution
V0.1	05/04/2022	First outline released	KNAW
V0.2	24/05/2022	Second version	KNAW
V0.21	08/06/2022	Processing of remarks made by reviewers	KNAW
V0.3	03/10/2022	Remarks by reviewers and observations during 5th Community meeting Paris taken into account	KNAW
V0.4	20/10/2022	Last reviewer comments	KNAW
V1.0	25/10/2022	Version submitted to coordinator	KNAW
V1.0	28/10/2022	Submission to EU	UNIBO

Table of contents

Project information	3
Project contacts	3
POLIFONIA consortium	3
Executive summary	5
Document history	6
1. Introduction – DMP practices in Polifonia	9
1.1. Data management policy of the Polifonia project	9
1.2. First to the second version of the DMP - Data management practices as inherent part of Polifonia's everyday life	9
1.3. First to the second version of the DMP - Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP)	10
1.3.1. What is an ORDP?	10
1.3.2. How does Polifonia apply the ORDP?	11
2. Polifonia Data Management Plan - Open Research Data Pilot	13
2.1. Data Summary	13
2.1.1. Survey	13
2.1.2. Data sources created and used by the 10 pilots (updated Table)	14
2.1.3. Polifonia Data sources as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem	14
2.2. FAIR Data	15
2.2.1. Polifonia Ontology Network (PON)	15
2.2.2. Polifonia Knowledge Graph (PKG)	16
2.2.2.1 Requirements for Knowledge Graph providers	18
2.2.3. The Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science	20
2.2.3.1. Actual version of the Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science	20
2.2.4. FAIR protocol sections in Deliverables	25
2.2.5. Polifonia Software Deliverable Guidelines and Software deliverable checklist	26
2.2.5.1. Actual version of the Software deliverable checklist for reviewers	26
2.3. Allocation of Resources	27
2.3.1. The Polifonia Github community	27
2.3.2. The Polifonia Ecosystem	28
2.3.2.1. Purpose	28
2.3.2.2. Design	29
2.3.2.3. Ecosystem Website	29
2.3.2.4. Ecosystem Rulebook	31
2.3.2.4.1. Current version of the Rulebook for the Polifonia Ecosystem	32

2.3.2.4.2. Current version of the Ecosystem Component Annotation Schema (as part of the Ecosystem rulebook)	36
2.3.2.5. Technical Board	40
2.3.3. The Polifonia Portal	40
2.4. Data Security	41
2.4.1. Polifonia Zenodo Community	41
2.4.1.1. Polifonia Zenodo Guidelines (version September 2022)	42
2.5. Ethical Aspects - Licences	45
2.6. Other Aspects - How do guidelines relate to each other?	46
2.6.1. Polifonia's documentation strategy: platforms	47
2.6.2. Interdependencies of guidelines	48
3. Outlook - How to further improve data management in Polifonia? - Towards the DMP version 3	49
Appendix 1: Overview of the main sources used in the pilots	51
Appendix 2: FAIR Protocol section in Deliverables	61
Mail of the coordinator	61
FAIR Protocol sections	62
D1.2 Roadmap and pilot requirements 2nd version	62
D1.9: Polifonia Web portal - 1st version (V1.0)	63
D2.4: Methods for interlinking knowledge graphs (V1.0)	63
D2.7: Ontology testing and evaluation report; knowledge graph documentation and access interfaces (V1.0)	64
D3.3: Software Tools for Mining Patterns in Music Repositories (V1.0)	65
D4.2 : Interrogation and annotation of plurilingual corpora for discourse analysis (V1.0)	66
Appendix 3: Overview on licences using in PILOTS and beyond - so-called file "External datasets requests"	69
References	71

1. Introduction – DMP practices in Polifonia

1.1. Data management policy of the Polifonia project

The mission of the Polifonia project is to provoke a paradigm shift in Musical Heritage preservation policies, management practice, research methodologies, interaction means and promotion strategies. Polifonia intends to achieve this goal by developing computing approaches that facilitate access and discovery of European Musical Heritage and enable a creative reuse of musical heritage at-scale.¹ The project is driven by ten pilot use cases addressing preservation, management, studying musical heritage and interacting with it.²

As detailed in the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (Admiraal et al. 2021), practices of data management are part of the overall management of the project. This has been designed into the project proposal by explicit cross-connections between the WP1 (the Socio-Technical Roadmap), WP6 (Dissemination and Outreach) and WP 8 (DMP).

The DMP version 1 (DMPv1) evaluated the source materials used in the pilots, and listed the envisioned (data) products of Polifonia itself - in particular the components of the designed Polifonia Ecosystem (Daga et al. 2021).

The DMP version 2 (DMPv2) documents the practices of data management implemented in the project so far, including documentation on the now implemented Polifonia Ecosystem and its components.

1.2. First to the second version of the DMP - Data management practices as inherent part of Polifonia's everyday life

Due the substantial resources Polifonia reserved for DM in the project (12PM during the whole project), DANS as the task lead of the DMP was able to provide close and at hand **Data Stewardship** with the aim to support the Working package leads, the pilot leads, the Technical Board and the Coordinator in establishing data management practices on a regular and explicit basis. As a result, data management is neither an afterthought of research processes, nor restricted to documentation.

This table details the methods applied in the making of the two DMP versions

DMP version 1 (M1-M6)	DMP version 2 (M7-M18/M22)
Structured interviews with Pilots leaders	Attendance in the WP1-WP5 weekly meetings, and other (review) meetings
Co-designing the survey (DMP relevant questions)	Data mining the survey ³
Participatory observation in project meetings	continued
Contributions to the Socio-Technical Roadmap	continued
Commenting on Deliverables	Continued and extended new: Designing a FAIR section template to be added to each Deliverable from M18 onwards (see

¹ <https://polifonia-project.eu/about/>

² <https://polifonia-project.eu/pilots/>

³ <https://github.com/polifonia-project/survey>

	section <i>FAIR Data</i> below)
	Participation in the Technical Board meeting
	Organisation of a webinar on FAIR data practices (DL 7.4) M10
	Organisation of a DMP awareness session at the 2th Polifonia Consortium meeting in Bologna M10
	Co-authoring/commenting on various guidelines

In the section 2 *Polifonia Data Management Plan - ORDP* the achievements which resulted from those methods are further detailed. The next subsection introduces the ORDP again and then gives an overview about main changes in content between DMPv1 and DMPv2.

1.3. First to the second version of the DMP - Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP)

1.3.1. What is an ORDP?

The DMP of Polifonia is based on the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) template, initiated by the European Commission⁴ to enable open access and reuse of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects.

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a formal document that specifies how research data will be handled both during and after a research project. It identifies key actions and strategies to ensure that research data are of a high quality, safe, sustainable and – where possible – accessible and reusable.⁵ For H2020 a DMP template⁶ is available that consists of the following components (see Figure 1 :

- A summary of the data
- How to make the data FAIR
- Information about costs and resources
- Information about data security

⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-the-open-research-data-pilot>

⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-a-data-management-plan-and-how-do-i-create-one>

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

1. DATA SUMMARY	2. FAIR DATA	3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	4. DATA SECURITY	5. ETHICAL ASPECTS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the purpose of the data collection/ generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? • What types and formats of data will the project generate/ collect? • Will you re-use any existing data and how? • What is the origin of the data? • What is the expected size of the data? • To whom might it be useful ('data utility')? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making data findable, including provisions for metadata (versions, keywords, naming conventions) • Making data openly accessible • Making data interoperable (ontologies) • Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? • How will these be covered? • Who will be responsible for data management in your project? • Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)? • Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). • Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Figure 1: Overview about the parts of an ORDP

1.3.2. How does Polifonia apply the ORDP?

What are the “outputs of the project” and which data is “collected, processed and generated by the project” has proven to be a complex question. Polifonia deals with a range of types of data objects that include text data, (such as spreadsheets, datasets, graph databases), software, models, and audio files. The data objects are both existing and created within the project. During the course of the project the features of the data objects to be managed become more clear.

These data objects are part of the **Polifonia Ecosystem**⁷ (a specially curated part of the **Polifonia Github instance**⁸), which has been implemented and which content is now emerging), the **Polifonia Zenodo community**⁹, the **Polifonia Portal**¹⁰ and the Polifonia server (hosted at the University of Bologna). The Polifonia project creates platforms on which components (data and tools) can be traced, researched and made accessible for a wider public.

The semantic nature of the research done in Polifonia, meaning the creation of a Polifonia Knowledge Graph¹¹ based on a Polifonia Ontology¹², inherently requires the FAIRness of data and tools. Without machine readable open data, there is no Knowledge Graph which can be later queried, and without building on existing ontologies the Polifonia Ontology, although originally in itself, would not expand the conceptualisation and research exploration in the field of musicology and musical heritage.

⁷ <https://github.com/polifonia-project/ecosystem>

⁸ <https://github.com/polifonia-project>

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/polifonia/?page=1&size=20>

¹⁰ Still in design, but see section 2.3.3. for snapshots

¹¹ The Polifonia Knowledge Graph emerges as more and more data are made available as Linked Open Data, using PON and providing Sparql endpoints for machine interaction. (see section 2.2.2 for more information)

¹² <https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-network>

For knowledge engineering to work, the understanding, documenting and negotiating of licence issues is crucial. Hence, as an important part DMPv2 also entails as the licence landscape exploration made by the WP1 team together with the pilots (see section 2.5).

Given the inherent importance of the FAIR principles, in the period between DMPv1 and DMPv2 a number of **guidelines** were developed to reinforce the FAIR data practices (see below). Their current versions are integrated into the respective sections of the ORDP. They range from almost common-sense Open Science Principles (see section 2.2.3) to a guide on how to use the Polifonia server for Linked Data publication (which is not public because of cybersecurity reasons). The function of the DMPv2 is to create an overview on all existing guidelines, when and how they are supposed to be applied and how they interlink with each other (see section 2.6). As Polifonia moves further we adapt those guidelines in parallel with monitoring their implementation in daily practice.

Figure 2 below lists the tangible outcomes of the DMPv2 in comparison with DMPv1, aligned with corresponding ORDP sections.

DMP Version 1 to 2

From PILOT survey, awareness raising, formulating OS principles to Polifonia's Data Management Cycle and Guidelines

ORDP - section	DMP Version 1	DMP Version 2
Data Summary 2.1.	Data sources description Pilots Co-design of survey	Survey (iterated, extended and data-mined) 2.1.1. Data sources Pilots (updated Table) 2.1.2. Polifonia Data sources as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem 2.1.3.
FAIR Data 2.2.	FAIR aspects discussion per Pilot	Polifonia Ontology Network 2.2.1. Polifonia Knowledge Graph 2.2.2. The Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science 2.2.3. FAIR protocol sections 2.2.4. Polifonia Software Guidelines 2.2.5. (including Software deliverable checklist)
Allocation of Resources 2.3.	Design of the Polifonia Ecosystem	Polifonia GitHub instance 2.3.1. Implementation of the Polifonia Ecosystem 2.3.2. (including Rulebook and Annotation scheme) Polifonia Portal 2.3.3.
Data Security 2.4.	Design of the Polifonia Ecosystem	Polifonia Zenodo community 2.4.1. (including Guidelines)
Ethical Aspects 2.5.	-	Licences 2.5.
Other Aspects 2.6.	Awareness raising (webinar)	Polifonia's documentation strategy 2.6.1. Intependencies of guidelines Overviews as Appendices Updated Table on Pilot sources/ FAIR protocol section (for DL's) / Overview on Licences

Figure 2: Comparison of content DMP version 1 and 2

In the next sections of the DMPv2 we describe each of those tangible outcomes in detail.

Please note that the Polifonia GitHub instance and in particular the **Polifonia Ecosystem** are leading in the data management practices. However, to align the DMPv2 with the ORDP template, the description of the Polifonia main outcomes appear in different sections:

- **Polifonia Ecosystem** as part of the **Polifonia Github instance** (2.3.)
- **Polifonia Zenodo community** (2.4., as Zenodo is used as main repository)
- **Polifonia Portal** (2.3.)

Moreover, aspects of those platforms also appear in other sections. For instance, some component types of the Polifonia Ecosystem are discussed already earlier 2.1. under section 'Data summary'. To support the

orientation of the reader the following Figure 3 lists again in which (sub)sections the platforms are addressed.

Figure 3: Overview about the platforms Polifonia uses and in which section of the DMPv2 they are discussed

2. Polifonia Data Management Plan - Open Research Data Pilot

2.1. Data Summary

2.1.1. Survey

The Polifonia Survey¹³ is the main tool to gather and store information about the pilots. It has been extended concerning its questions, and content is updated regularly. Currently, we operate with version 4. The Survey is one of three knowledge management tools (called SMS, which is short for Stories-Manipasta-Survey) (Guillotel-Nothmann et al. 2021). The Survey was developed at the start of the project. Stories stands for the development of use scenarios of Polifonia’s products (archetypical users and uses). Manipasta stands for a series of hackathons which take place to bring all the developers together around very tangible demonstrators and proof of concepts. We focus here on the Survey as this tool has been co-designed from a data management perspective, and is also data-mined for this Data Management Plan (see Appendix 1).

“The Survey is structured in three key areas. In the first area, the Domain Specific part, each pilot is asked to identify and to define the characterization of the sources and to list the available digital corpora or datasets. The second key area deals with the Technical part of the dataset(s) and has three main goals: 1) to identify the current practices of the consortium in terms of the use of data formats and standards that ensure the expression of the meaning of these data; 2) to identify among the pilots the broad strategies for

¹³ <https://github.com/polifonia-project/survey>

producing new knowledge and articulating it to existing knowledge in the context of the Web and Linked Open Data for cultural heritage; 3) to identify the software processes and artefacts that will make the data meaningful for users, in particular the expectations in terms of data access and visualisation on the Polifonia Web portal. The third key area focuses on the Socio-pedagogical aspect of the pilots and/or dataset(s), identifying the target groups (amateurs, musicians, students, etc.) and their conditions (disabilities, specific reference person for the pilot's socio-pedagogical implications)."

The Survey (live document) has been published on GitHub¹⁴, and regularly backed up in Zenodo as Dataset (Guillotel-Nothmann et al. 2022a). A Knowledge Graph representation of the Survey is currently produced, which allows to integrate the concepts behind the Survey design into the Polifonia Ontology Network and to display relevant content as part of the Polifonia Knowledge graph (see: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/survey-kg>)

2.1.2. Data sources created and used by the 10 pilots (updated Table)

In Appendix 1 (Table on pilots) we document changes in the source description of the pilots resulting from the survey and other documents. To mark the progress in information gathering new edits are red coloured.

As detailed in the DMPv1 (Admiraal et al., 2021), Polifonia consists of 10 pilots, which are different in nature. The Polifonia survey addressed the pilot leaders and asked them for information on the sources (data), methods and goals they follow. In the survey the pilot leaders give answers on the level of the whole pilot. But, some pilots work with a variety of sources. So, we have information on pilot level and on 'data collection' or 'dataset' level. This became already visible in the interviews conducted for DMPv1 which lead to a table with DMP relevant information (see Appendix 1).

As Polifonia progresses data sources from the pilots are more and more integrated into the Polifonia output. This means that a data management plan based on the pilots, as we produced in the DMPv1 is no longer adequate. Sources from the pilots are augmented and merge into the Polifonia Ecosystem. In this process of integration, source material is published in the Polifonia GitHub instance, partly also annotated as a component of the Polifonia Ecosystem. Sources and their enrichment are described in greater detail in deliverables, and, if appropriate, stored as 'raw data' in the Polifonia Zenodo community. In parallel, pilots are in the process to provide Linked Data as part of the Polifonia Knowledge Graph. Those Linked Data are available via SPARQL endpoints, either hosted by a consortium member who originated/maintains the data from which the Linked Data publication derives, or by the Polifonia server hosted at UNIBO (see section 2.2.2). Still, to enable a comparison between DMPversion 1 and 2, we provided an updated version of the original table. This table represents one could say the pilot perspective on the sources. But, as data sources also are part of the Polifonia GitHub repository, the Polifonia Ecosystem, and the Polifonia Portal we also describe those platforms in detail (see section 2.3. *Allocation of resources*).

2.1.3. Polifonia Data sources as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem

The Polifonia Ecosystem contains different types of components (see section 2.3. *Allocation of Resources*, subsection 2.3.1. *The Polifonia Ecosystem* for a complete list).

¹⁴ <https://github.com/polifonia-project/survey>

The Table below lists all subcategories under the category **Data**, their current population, and possible releases into Zenodo. Please note that only specific resources are 'accredited' (that means: selected, annotated and evaluated) to become part of the Polifonia Ecosystem.

Data components (as any other components) are annotated according to the **rulebook**¹⁵ (see section 2.3.2.4.1) and the Annotation scheme which has been developed as part of the rulebook (see section 2.3.2.4.2). For Data a **licence field** is required. Data produced as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem are regularly backed up in Zenodo. (see section 2.3.2. *The Polifonia Ecosystem*)

The following table lists all Polifonia Ecosystem components of the category Data, according to the used subcategories (for the whole structure and the definition of the labels see section *The Polifonia Ecosystem*) by end of September 2022. The last column checks for releases of components into Zenodo. Please note that the Technical Board is currently monitoring the use of this category system and might adapt the system if need be.

Data	#	Links to components in this subcategory	Zenodo backup
Registry			
Ontology			
Dataset	3	Documentary evidence benchmark Listening Experience Database musoW	X X
Repository	4	FONN - Folk N-gram aNalysis Root Note Detection Local Harmonic Agreement based on Recurrent Patterns Textual Corpus Population	all
Corpus	1	Ceol Rince na hÉireann MIDI corpus	
Knowledge Graph			

2.2. FAIR Data

2.2.1. Polifonia Ontology Network (PON)

"The Polifonia Ontology Network, a set of OWL ontology modules to describe the content and context of tangible and intangible musical cultural heritage assets from Europe. Included modules are: Core, Musical Performance, Musical Composition, Musical Feature, Source, Instrument, Comparative Measure, Music

¹⁵ <https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>

Emotion, Metadata, Bell.” (Carriero et al., 2022) Its development takes place in the Polifonia Github instance, and it is part of the Polifonia Ecosystem. Figure 4 gives an overview of the structure of PON.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the modules in the Polifonia Ontology network

The design of the PON is both unique and conservative. *Unique* (agnostic) here means that PON serves the innovative approach of Polifonia and so simple re-use of existing ontologies is not possible. At same time it is also *conservative* meaning that it bases on a thorough review of existing ontologies (in the fields of musicological research, musicological heritage and semantic web) (see <https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-network/blob/main/d21-ontologies.pdf> for an overview.) “This ensures an agnostic approach in which Polifonia designs a specific conceptualisation of music (elements, reception, actors, events, etc.) that reflects original and innovative theory building aspirations, while providing a good compromise with respect to reusing existing models and theories.” (Meroño Peñuela et al. 2021)

2.2.2. Polifonia Knowledge Graph (PKG)

The PKG is a network of distributed, machine-readable web-based resources of Linked Data (expressed in PON). “The Polifonia Knowledge Graph uses the ontologies of the PON to annotate and interlink large European music collections as a Knowledge Graph.” (Meroño Peñuela et al. 2021). In short, the PKG is the populated PON. Progress on the actual construction and evaluation of the PKG has been reported in D2.4. (Meroño Peñuela et al. 2022).

For the PKG to be able to function, all resources in the graph need to be deployed on the web. In summer 2022 an inventory was started to list and monitor the distributed network on Knowledge Graph providers. Many of the Polifonia consortium members already provide SPARQL endpoints themselves together with commitments of maintenance for those access points, and equipped with appropriate licences (see section 2.5. *Ethical Aspects*). For Linked Data producers without access to a (long-term stable) server, UNIBO offered to host the data on a specifically dedicated Polifonia server, and provided an (internal) document of access to the server.

The progress on SPARQL endpoints provision about the pilots is monitored by the working group "Knowledge Graph Providers"¹⁶. The table below shows the status of resources by September 1, 2022. Colour coding has been applied to show the different service providers and how these resources are documented. We mark the Polifonia Github repository (light green), Zenodo (light yellow) and hosted by consortium members (dark green).

Dataset	Repo Link	SPARQL link	Docs link	Ontology	Notes
BELLS	here	here	here	here	Published on a platform of a consortium member, some few datasets might need hosting on the central Polifonia server
MUSICBO	here			here and here	To be published on the Polifonia server First version (some data) will be available in September 2022
ChoCo	Private repo			JAMS Ontology	Needs alignment to PON To be published on the Polifonia server
musoW	here	here	here	Schema.org	Needs alignment to PON Status: ready to use, will be updated 500 web resources w/ 40ish fields each
FACETS					Datasets come from publicly available data, and are reached through a REST interface (A1, I1-I2, R1 principles). Unsure about A2, I3.
MEETUPS	GitHub				Needs alignment to PON
CHILD	(same as LED)	(same as LED)	(same as LED)	(same as LED)	(same as LED)
LED		http://data.open.ac.uk/sparql (named graph "http://data.open.ac.uk/context/led")			Needs alignment to PON Status: ready to use, will be updated
ORGANS	here	here		Ad Hoc dump of data into PON	Needs alignment to PON This data is derived from the full text of the Organ Encyclopaedia, which is not publicly available. This data should also not be publicly available, only within the project.
TUNES	Same as WP3	Same as WP3	Same as WP3 pattern network	Same as WP3 pattern network	

¹⁶ Internal document in the Polifonia UNIBO Sharepoint instance
https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/polifonia/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B53236EE2-32AC-4FEB-957D-467AB887DDAF%7D&file=Knowledge%20Graph%20Providers.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true&DefaultItemOpen=1 (not public)

	pattern network	pattern network		+bibliographic ad hoc	
TONALITIES	here		here	here	Needs alignment to PON Needs alignment to CQ in Sethus Stories
INTERLINK					
FoNN					Assumably easy to be aligned with PON, mostly bibliographic information
Music pattern network	KG			Here	-Needs documentation
NISV 78RPM and concert collections	Example subset here	here (among other data)		Schema.org	-Needs alignment to PON Needs documentation Concepts are part of a larger data source, the two specific collections cannot yet be queried separately published under an open license
MIDI LDC					
Consortium	Github	Zenodo	Others		COLORCODING

Requirements have been formulated for each Knowledge Graph provider (see section 2.2.2.1).

The Polifonia Knowledge Graph production follows closely the discourse of the W3C Dataset Exchange Working Group which formed around DCAT and focuses on “interoperability between services such as data catalogues, e-Infrastructures and virtual research environments”¹⁷. Best practice information is also conveyed by membership of one Data Steward (Andrea Scharnhorst) in the EOSC Semantic Interoperability TaskForce, and by participation of both Data Stewards (Rene van Horik and Andrea Scharnhorst) in the FAIR-Impact Project.¹⁸

2.2.2.1 Requirements for Knowledge Graph providers

Repository requirements

A SPARQL endpoint including your data (whether these are some toy data or an intermediate version of your current data) is needed by September 1, 2022. If you do not have means to transform/publish your data in a graph store, please be in touch with people in WP2 for data transformation, and with marilena.daquino2@unibo.it for publishing your data on the polifonia server.

- Repo: link to a copy of data (Linked Open Data!) in a github repository and/or in a dedicated folder of the repository
- Files: If the data volume exceeds 500MB, split data into different files
- Serialisation: If data are difficult to split, use ntriples / quads serialisation. Otherwise any.
- SPARQL endpoint: provide the link to the SPARQL endpoint that include or will include your data at the deadline of September 1, 2022. Should you need support in publishing data, e.g. on the Polifonia server, include a note here.

Documentation requirements

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/2022/06/dx-wg-charter.html>

¹⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu>

Documentation: provide a link to the documentation of your data. This can be a web page, a README file, etc. and should include the following:

- *MUST: describe briefly the scope of the dataset (the number of main entities - e.g. organs, people, songs - and the rough number of descriptive fields / properties for these)*
- *MUST: a description of the data model you used (classes, predicates)*
- *SHOULD: include the licence for data reuse (hence responsible people)*
- *SHOULD: example queries*
- *SHOULD: a graphical representation of classes and predicates*

If you have this information scattered in several places, for the moment is fine (as long as you fill in the table above), but please remember that at some point you'll need to upload your data in Zenodo for long-term preservation, so you must produce this documentation anyway.

Notes

Please, use the notes to provide information about the status of data by September 1, 2022. Do not include information about non-linked open data. By that date we need data as LOD.

- *Alignment: Record whether the data need alignment to the PON ontology*
- *Status: what is the current status of the dataset, whether it is ready to use, if it is reasonably complete, or it just includes*
- *Estimate the scope: the number of main entities (e.g. organs, people) and the number of descriptive fields for these entities, at the estimated due date of September 1, 2022.*

78RPM – number of programs

```
SELECT (count(?program) as ?c)
WHERE {
```

```
?series <https://schema.org/name> "Muziekopnamen Zendgemachtigden (MOZ)"^^xsd:string .
?season sdo:partOfSeries ?series .
?program sdo:partOfSeason ?season .
}
```


2.2.3. The Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science

At the Bologna meeting October 2021 of the Polifonia consortium, a special session was held about good data management practices and the concrete need emerged to bring together a kind of checklist for good open science practices. The current version of this list can be found in section 2.2.3.1. The list represents a combination of common-sense Open Science Principles, such as the use of PID where appropriate and more domain specific advice (concerning knowledge engineering). The Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science primarily address issues of bibliographic documentation. They complement and inform other guidelines which direct specific actions, such as the rulebook for the Polifonia Ecosystem, the guide to review software deliverables, the instruction for Knowledge Graph providers, the Zenodo guide etc.. In section 2.6 *Other Aspects* we give an overview on the use of platforms and guidelines in Polifonia.

2.2.3.1. Actual version of the Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science

(as of October 2022)¹⁹

Overview

R1: Polifonia requires that all essential components of the Polifonia Ecosystem are registered in the Polifonia github community.

R2: Polifonia recommends to use Zenodo to register output.

R3: Organise access to your resources via the Polifonia Portal/Polifonia server

R4: Use your ORCID to identify you as an author!

R5: Acknowledge the grant (the Polifonia project) with each output!

R6: Use DOI's to refer to work you produce!

R7: For datasets you think are important cornerstones of your work deposit them into the Polifonia Ecosystem (see R1). Consider archiving 'authoritative versions' into a certified data repository!

R8: Authorship/publication Netiquette

R9: R9: Adhere FAIR principles and licencing principles

R10: If in doubt: Ask the DataManagers of your institutions and consult the DataStewards of Polifonia (DANS-KNAW)!

Preamble

The process of research is sometimes described as a pipeline containing INPUT – the Research process itself – and OUTPUT. Although this is just a very simple model and in practice the processes are much more circular [1] and messy [2], it can help to organise the documentation process.

Definitions

INPUT= all preconditions of research such as instruments/servers/..., institutions, funds and staff involved

PROCESS BOX = all research processes

OUTPUT = all tangible output such as Publications, but also Presentations, Proceedings papers, certain software packages etc.

¹⁹ Internal document:

https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/w:/r/sites/polifonia/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7BF246F152-D645-491A-BAB2-76AE9C78A690%7D&file=OpenScience_10Rules.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true&DefaultItemOpen=1

Please note that 'data' [4] can appear in all of the phases: collections we use as source material (Input), datasets/ontologies we produce as part of the research process and publish for possible re-use, and data collections enriched which are hosted and possibly archive for the mid and long-term. In the digital age, all three phases can be better traced and borders between the three phases also become blurry. In particular, more of the actual research process can be recorded and possibly also archived. [3] So, the Process Box – formerly perceived as a black box becomes much more visible, and intermediate results become objects worth to be documented too (think here of workflows, survey design and so on). Polifonia is embracing these possibilities while adhering to the principles of Open Science, Open Access and Fairness.

This document "Polifonia's 10 Rules for Open Science" contains guidelines for proper bibliographic referencing across platforms Polifonia uses for documentation (see section *Allocation of Resources*. But, it also applies to other platforms Polifonia consortium members might want or need to use for their own personal or institutional research information management (think here of your personal website, or ResearchInformationSystems your university uses). By these 10 Rules, Polifonia obliges the requirements to Open Access as defined in the GrantAgreement [5] .

This document functions as a checklist and is published as part of the DataManagementPlan version2, which in itself explains in greater detail documentation workflows in Polifonia.

R1: Polifonia requires that all essential components of the Polifonia Ecosystem are registered in the Polifonia github community.

Use the Polifonia GitHub for your code production, and document everything which is a component of the Polifonia Ecosystem according to the rulebook, so that your steps are transparent and reproducible!

The Ecosystem entails "anything that is not a research paper, dissemination product (e.g., video presentation of a tool), or deliverable ". The [Rulebook](#) contains "Guidelines, recommendations, and norms on how to contribute to the Polifonia Ecosystem". defines what, when and how components to the Ecosystem. It defines a [schema](#) how to annotate components. Regularly, from the Polifonia Ecosystem releases are selected for a machine executed submission to the Polifonia Zenodo community. Please note that the Rulebook is also a dynamical document. The Technical Board of Polifonia supervised the documentation process, and makes decisions on which form should be integrated in, or linked to the Polifonia Portal.

Cross-check with [Polifonia Software Deliverable Guide](#) and the internal checklist for reviewers for software deliverables. [6]

R2: Polifonia recommends to use Zenodo to register output.

Follow the **Polifonia Zenodo upload guide** to upload your content into the Polifonia Zenodo community. Please, register all items listed in various (internal) [dissemination tables](#) (such as papers (preferably with preprints/author-version); presentations; and [deliverables](#) (reports).

R3: Organise access to your resources via the Polifonia Portal/Polifonia server

The Technical Board of Polifonia supervises the documentation process, and makes decisions on which form should be integrated in, or linked to the Polifonia Portal. The University of Bologna (hosting the

Polifonia server) produces an updated technical guide (as an internal document) on how to use the Polifonia server for consortium members (external to the UB).

A working group "Knowledge graph providers" has been set up, which defines requirements for LinkedData repositories (a type of Polifonia Ecosystem components, with an extended/minimum set of annotations) and their required documentation. These KOS service provisions are traced by using an internal [table](#).

R4: Use your ORCID to identify you as an author!

ORCID=PID for authors

PID enables machines to bring information together; ORCID allows you to register also other Author PID you might have, such as a SCOPUS ID; it has become a standard.

You can register your ORCID personally - sometimes institutions register their employees. if you not have one yet - register today. <https://orcid.org>

Many other platforms ask you for your ORCID (Zenodo, or Conference organisers). The more you use it, the more of your content is marked with a specific, authoritative identifier.

The Polifonia Zenodo Upload Guide contains an example. ORCID's of all Polifonia contributors are provided as part of an internal document to trace all Deliverables (see [here](#)).

R5: Acknowledge the grant (the Polifonia project) with each output!

This way the Polifonia project remains visible, and all output ever produced under the project is marked.

Use the standard sentence "*This work has been (partly) enabled by the H2020 Project Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge funded by the European Commission Grant number 101004746*". Use an acknowledgement section for it. Be aware that you can mention different grants in one acknowledgement, acknowledging numerous funding sources.

Be aware that the Polifonia Grant number **101004746** is a PID too, this time provided by the European Commission. So, in Zenodo for instance, you are required to add this in a specific field (see the Polifonia Zenodo upload guide); also many journals ask you for that in their specific metadata schemes. Content from Polifonia is harvested in systems as OpenAire and a profile of Polifonia can be made visible <https://explore.openaire.eu/search/find?active=projects&fvo=101004746&fo=q>.

R6: Use DOI's to refer to work you produce!

In short: a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) is a PID for a piece of 'work'.

https://www.doi.org/registration_agencies.html DOI are used by publishers, but also Zenodo issues DOI's for content uploaded, and many (data) repositories do.

DOI is a PID for a whole bibliographic reference, while ORCID and GRANT# are PID's for part of the reference.

See <https://zenodo.org/record/5483727#.YWWgCSorPwM> as an example

R7: For datasets you think are important cornerstones of your work deposit them into the Polifonia Ecosystem (see R1). Consider archiving 'authoritative versions' into a certified data repository! Preferably a repository which is certified, issues a DOI, and offers version control.

Polifonia recommends the use of the Electronic Archiving System (DANS-KNAW)

<https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/ui/home> and The Digital repository of Ireland <https://dri.ie/about-dri#>, both CoreTrustSeal certified. Polifonia also accepts any other repository which a community members might host/use provided it adheres to a certified standard.

Data Repositories which are also obliged to DataCite principles are listed here: <https://www.re3data.org>

For certified repositories see: <https://www.coretrustseal.org>

For European Archives check also: <https://www.archivesportaleurope.net/home> Your archive could be there without your knowing ;-)

Familiarize yourself with data citation practices in your field, and cite research data accordingly!

R8: Authorship/publication Netiquette

Polifonia is a multidisciplinary project, where disciplines come with different norms/rules where, when and with whom to publish. Acknowledge collaboration always (depending on size and substance of a collaboration by co-authorship, or at least by an acknowledgement); Ask your group members in which form they would like to be acknowledged! Be alert to make also 'invisible work' (supporting work) visible too!

The Technical Board of Polifonia supervised the documentation process, and makes decision what in which form should be integrated in, or linked to the Polifonia Ecosystem and later the Polifonia Portal.

R9: Adhere FAIR principles and licencing principles

In particular obliged²⁰:

- Provide a persistent URI (PURL, DOI, w3id) for the resource (and related results)
- Provide a canonical citation associated with the resource
- Provide a licence specification (See creativecommons.org, opensource.org for more information, Consult <https://www.openaire.eu/how-do-i-license-my-research-data> for general issues on data licencing. Inform yourself about licences used in the musicology domain (see DMP version2, Appendix VII)
- Indicate whether and where the resource is publicly available. For example as API, Linked Open Data, Download, Open Code Repository (the GitHub repository will work here).
- Make the resource publicly findable by registering it in (community) registries (e.g. Linked Open Vocabularies, BioPortal, DataHub or others). Indicate if and where it is registered in generic repositories such as FigShare, Zenodo or GitHub. The two latter recommended by Polifonia
- Discuss your thought or plan for sustainability of the resource including the medium and long-term maintenance of the resource
- Indicate whether and which open standards the resource adopts (when applicable). Alternatively, motivate why it does not adopt standards.

For FAIRness of Semantic artefacts please, consult also

²⁰ Personal communication Coordinator, Mail of June 16, 2022

- How to publish sources as LOD read “Linked Open Data - 10 Things to reach the realm of LOD” - which is a popular ‘translation’ of the W3C recommendation <https://zenodo.org/record/3471806#.YWXCJioRpWM>
- Inform yourself about state-of-art FAIR recommendations [see FAIRsFAIR on semantic artefacts <https://zenodo.org/record/5356630#.YWFxtyoRpWM>. Those recommendations are generic, technology and domain agnostic but give an orientation.
- Test your objects! F-UJI tool <https://www.f-ujl.net> (With this tool you can test the FAIRness of anything which has an URL/PID/DOI!)
- Report your SPARQL endpoints to the Polifonia Portal (see guide for Knowledge Graph providers (section), include document sustainability strategies for machine-readable, life information produced!
- OWL use for Polifonia Knowledge Graph -> check with WP2 and Technical Board
- For further practical tips for FAIR data management:
 - LCRDM: <https://www.lcrdm.nl/en/23things>
 - PARTHENOS guidelines: <https://zenodo.org/record/3368858#.YVcADC8Ro8Q>
 - CESSDA guide: <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Expert-Guide>

R10: If in doubt: Ask the DataManagers of your institutions and consult the DataStewards of Polifonia (DANS-KNAW)!

References

- [1] Admiraal, Femmy, Scharnhorst, Andrea, Daga, Enrico, Daquino, Marilena, Musumeci, Elena, Kranenburg, Peter, Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, Gurrieri, Marco, Presutti, Valentina, Clementi, Marta, Meroño Peñuela, Albert, Turci, Monica, Marzi, Eleonora, Puglisi, Antonio, & Fournier-S'niehotta, Raphaël. (2021). D7.1 First Data Management Plan (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6963585>
- [2] P. Wouters, K. Vann, A. Scharnhorst, M. Ratto, I. Hellsten, J. Fry, and A. Beaulieu (2008) Messy shapes of knowledge - STS explores informatization, new media, and academic work. The Virtual Knowledge Studio. In: The Handbook of Science and Technology Studies, edited by E. J. Hackett, O. Amsterdamska, M. Lynch and J. Wajcman. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press. 319-352.
- [3] Van de Sompel, H., and Treloar, A. (2014) A Perspective on Archiving the Scholarly Web. Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Digital Preservation, iPres2014 ; [self-archived copy](#)
- [4] C. Borgman, Little Data, Big Data, No Data. Scholarship in the Networked World. MIT 2015
- [5] Document Ref. Ares(2020)5825178 - 23/10/2020
Grant Agreement number: 101004746 — Polifonia — H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2018-2019-2020 / H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020; H2020 General MGA — Multi: v5
- [6] Diamond, Danny, Shahid, Abdul, & McDermott, James. (2022). D3.3: Software Tools for Mining Patterns in Music Repositories (V1.0) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118763>

Appendix

Quotations from the GrantAgreement: [5]

“29.2 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

(a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

- (b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - (i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - (ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- (c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:
 - the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
 - the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
 - the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
 - a persistent identifier.

29.3 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the beneficiaries must:

(a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:

- (i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;
- (ii) not applicable;
- (iii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan' (see Annex 1);

(b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data under Point (a)(i) and (iii), if the achievement of the action's main objective (as described in Annex 1) would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

2.2.4. FAIR protocol sections in Deliverables

Guided by the DMPv2 writing in May 2022, Polifonia decided to add a FAIR Protocol to each of the Deliverables from month 18 onwards. The authors of those deliverables were provided with a list of bullet points they were invited to address (see template below in the textbox). Data stewards participated in almost all review meetings, and were available for consultation in writing this section.

The function of this additional section to each upcoming Deliverable is multi-fold: 1. it raises awareness for FAIR issues in the research process documented in the Polifonia project; 2. it invites reflection and to report which aspects of FAIRification are already addressed; 3. it shows how the different means to ensure FAIR in Polifonia are coming together around concrete results; 4. It helps to indicate which open issues exist (on which The Technical Board and in particular the Data Stewards can act). We decided to list those sections, as they are great testimony and good examples (see Appendix 2: FAIR Protocol section in Deliverables).

The original aim was to develop the template further (see email communication in Appendix 2). During the 5th Polifonia Consortium meeting (Paris September 19-23, 2022) it was agreed that the Technical Board will discuss how these reported good practices could be represented in a kind of FAIR score for components of the Polifonia Ecosystem (kind of FAIR metrics). This discussion will most certainly lead to a

change in the current metadata model for components and further guidelines on how to generate content for them (rulebook). We will document this in the third version of the DMP.

To support this process, we continue to require the FAIR protocol section in all upcoming DL's.

Template

<p>FAIR protocol</p> <p>summarise with a list all components released as result of the work described in the report (this will be redundant but yet it's useful to have a bullet list with links all in one place)</p> <p>describe the practice and tools implemented to make them FAIR</p> <p>strategy for long-term persistence</p>
--

2.2.5. Polifonia Software Deliverable Guidelines and Software deliverable checklist

The Software deliverable checklist is an internal Polifonia checklist for software production, which has been developed in the context of D3.3. The idea is that in future reviewers will fill in this checklist for each software component related deliverable being reviewed. The items of this checklist are derived from the Polifonia Software Deliverable Guidelines https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook/blob/main/deliverable_guidelines.md which in turn are aligned with the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook.

2.2.5.1. Actual version of the Software deliverable checklist for reviewers²¹

Accessed version September 29, 2022

https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/polifonia/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B15BEA5D8-7FC3-4A1A-812C-8CAD237AECBD%7D&file=software-deliverable-checklist.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true&DefaultItemOpen=1

<Software title> <GitHub link>		Summary <n>/18 checks passed	
Required/desired part	Priority	Pass	Notes
Report: summary table	Must have		
Report: exploitability	Should have		
Report: future work	Nice to have		
GitHub: rulebook header	Should have		
GitHub: on Zenodo	Must have		

²¹ Has been developed during a review by Jacopo De Berardinis, later adapted by James McDermott, June 2022

GitHub: Zenodo release	Must have		
GitHub: has Zenodo DOI	Must have		
GitHub: includes license	Must have		
GitHub: clear README	Must have		
GitHub doc: abstract and highlights of the software	Must have		
GitHub doc: reference to Polifonia deliverable	Should have		
GitHub doc: citation of the software repository	Should have		
GitHub setup: list of package/lib requirements	Must have		
GitHub setup: instruction to setup the environment	Should have		
GitHub setup: data sources	Nice to have		
GitHub running: instructions for soft. use	Should have		
GitHub running: demo	Should have		
GitHub: Software testing	Nice to have		

2.3. Allocation of Resources

2.3.1. The Polifonia Github community

The Polifonia project has created a GitHub instance to coordinate resource development (both data and tools). <https://github.com/polifonia-project> While GitHub is a commercially available platform the software behind GitHub, GIT is open source²². So, in case of a termination of this specific service a contingency plan is possible. Additionally, Polifonia has taken specific measures to store important versions of work (again data and tools) in Zenodo by using an automatic pipeline between GitHub and Zenodo (see section 2.4. *Data Security* and Ecosystem Rulebook, section 2.3.2.4.1.). The Polifonia Github community enables the coordination of the project technologically, and so complements the Polifonia sharepoint instance which is not public and used for inner project coordination.

Currently, the Polifonia Github community has 46 participants, working on 61 repositories, most of which (57) are public. A GitHub repository contains all files which belong to a certain sub-project. As Figure 5

²² According to Wikipedia "**Git** ([/ɡɪt/](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Git)) is **free and open source software** for **distributed version control**: tracking changes in any set of files, usually used for coordinating work among programmers collaboratively developing source code during software development." (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Git> accessed October 1, 2022)

below shows, GitHub enables to trace activities in repositories. The most important current development projects are pinned.

Figure 5: Snapshot of the Polifonia Github instance (October 1, 2022)

2.3.2. The Polifonia Ecosystem

2.3.2.1. Purpose

The Polifonia Ecosystem represents the technological backbone of the Polifonia project, and it is implemented as part of the Polifonia Github instance. In other words, the Polifonia Ecosystem represents those parts of the GitHub documented resource production which are accredited as part of Deliverables (official outcomes of the projects). One could also say it is a specifically curated part of the Polifonia Github instance. But, its design goes beyond mere software development management. As stated in D1.3 (Daga et al. 2021) "The Polifonia Ecosystem is conceived as a collection of components which are both independent – they have some value on their own – and interlinked – they can be used together in order to satisfy specific end-user needs." The Ecosystem represents the main products and achievements of the Polifonia consortium. Its design has been informed by other knowledge management tools (as Stories²³, Maninpasta and Survey). Stories are one component type, and Maninpasta and Survey guide and inform the production of other components.

²³ The 'Stories' approach emerged from a combination of two methodological practices, one around the design of the Polifonia Knowledge Graph (WP2) and another around the design of the user interface (WP5). As D1.1. explains "The combination of these practices led to defining a story-based approach for the collection of Polifonia pilots' requirements. Practically, we provide pilot experts with a template to describe their *Stories* in a shared environment with the teams of developers." (Guillotet-Nothmann et al. 2021, section 1 Stories)

2.3.2.2. Design

Core of the Polifonia Ecosystem are components. Currently, the following types and subtypes of components are distinguished.

“What is a Polifonia Ecosystem *component*?”

Basically, anything that is not a research paper, dissemination product (e.g., video presentation of a tool), or deliverable.

List of component types:

Documentation:

- Persona (strictly from <https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>)
- Story (strictly from <https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>)
- Tutorial
- Documentation

Executables:

- Application
- Container
- Experiment
- CLI²⁴ tool

Reusable software:

- Library
- User Interface
- Service

Data:

- Registry
- Ontology
- Dataset
- Repository
- Corpus
- Knowledge Graph²⁵

2.3.2.3. Ecosystem Website

As Daga et al. 2022 write “the ecosystem is a collection of artefacts, which are inherently heterogeneous, i.e., registries, ontologies, knowledge graphs, software libraries, etc. Therefore, these component types are meant to be interlinked.” Next to interlinking there are also different ‘user groups’ envisioned (see Figure 6).

²⁴ CLI = Command Line Interface

²⁵ <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/polifonia-project/rulebook/README.html>

Figure 4.1: The Polifonia Ecosystem: overview of the components and main relations. Connection points in black represent connections to all the components.

Figure 6: Overview about the components of the Polifonia Ecosystem (reproduced from Daga et al. 2021)

To be able to navigate the Polifonia Ecosystem, to curate the components, and to navigate through the links between them, a website (running on the GitHub instance) has been created: <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/> (see below Figure 7)

Figure 7: Snapshot of the Polifonia Ecosystem website (build from GitHub content automatically)

2.3.2.4. Ecosystem Rulebook

The Polifonia Ecosystem Rulebook (see section 2.3.2.4.1.) governs which components are included in the Ecosystem at which point in time and with which purpose. As the Ecosystem rulebook states under the question “Do I really need to create a repository for anything I do? No. But as soon as the work is discussed or presented in a meeting a repository should be already there, or follow straight after! A repository with annotated component descriptions (see later) is mandatory for components mentioned in official deliverables.” The Ecosystem remains the main reference and documentation point for data and tool created by the project. Via the annotation scheme (which is a living document) and under the supervision of the Technical Board, data and tools are produced which oblige FAIR principles. The coupling with

Zenodo ensures the mid-term preservation and referencability of those sources. (see Rulebook "Register your repository on Zenodo, by activating the related GitHub Action. See [this guide](#)")

The Annotation Scheme, which is a Polifonia metadata standard to annotate components, is an important part of the Ecosystem. It also contains fields about licences. This scheme will be available as a Knowledge Graph, and together with a Knowledge Graph representation of the currently used licences (see Section 'Ethical Aspects') will enable to manage (and communicate to outside user communities) the accessibility of various resources.

2.3.2.4.1. Current version of the Rulebook for the Polifonia Ecosystem²⁶

Rulebook

Guidelines, recommendations, and norms on how to contribute to the Polifonia Ecosystem.

Guidelines

When to create a repository?

Create a GH repository whenever there is an activity which leads to the production of a *component* of the *Polifonia Ecosystem*.

Do I really need to create a repository for anything I do?

No. But as soon as the work is discussed or presented in a meeting a repository should be already there, or follow straight after! A repository with annotated component descriptions (see later) is mandatory for components mentioned in official deliverables.

What if a repository already exists somewhere else?

You don't need to fork the repository in the Polifonia organisation. External components can be described (with annotations) in the repository [external-components](#).

Champion

Each repository must have a champion. Champions need to be annotated in the [CHAMPIONS.md](#) file.

Discussion and decisions

Discussions can happen anywhere at anytime. However, decisions that impact the development of the component **MUST** be logged within an Issue (a Github issue, example) and motivated.

²⁶ <https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook> Version of September 30, 2022

If the decision is not being recorded in an Issue, **it never happened**.

Tracking changes (commits)

Commit messages are mandatory and must reference at least one Issue. A good commit message is `Added folder XYZ with data from QWE, see also #432` where #432 is the issue number in the same repository. You can also reference any URL in commit messages, please see GitHub documentation for examples. The more you link, the better.

Useful readings on best practices:

- <https://gist.github.com/luismts/495d982e8c5b1a0ced4a57cf3d93cf60#file-gitcommitbestpractices-md>
- <https://medium.com/@danielfeelfine/commit-verbs-101-why-i-like-to-use-this-and-why-you-should-also-like-it-d3ed2689ef70>

This is a [bad commit message](#) This is a [good commit message](#)

Tracking Progress Issue

Progress on the development of each component **MUST** be reported in the Issues section periodically. Each repository **SHOULD** have a single **Tracking Progress Issue** for general progress update. A simple reporting template can be a bullet list in three sections: Progress, Problems, and Perspectives (3P).

The 3P are:

- Progress: what concrete work has been done since the last update.
- Problems: anything that is slowing or blocking progress, or it is expected to do so.
- Perspectives: what progress is expected going forward, including plans that have been made to face any of the problems (if any).

Please note that the Tracking progress issue is only for updates. Detailed, task-based issues should be used for referencing changes (commits) and can be linked in the Tracking Progress Issue.

Examples:

- [Tracking progress issue \(Rulebook\)](#)
- [Tracking progress issue \(External Components\)](#)

Naming conventions

Some naming conventions have been discussed, feel free to contribute to the discussion [here](#)

For repositories

- Avoid including “Polifonia” in the name (e.g. `ecosystem` rather than `polifonia-ecosystem`)

- Avoid acronyms (`ontology-network` instead of `ON`)

Branches

Use branches for managing different versions of the code / components. Avoid creating a branch for each sub-system (e.g. /datasets /ui etc... Instead, create different repositories.

Releases

Use Semantic Versioning for release numbers, and follow the GitHub workflow for releasing.

Register your repository on Zenodo, by activating the related GitHub Action. See [this guide](#).

Contributing to the Ecosystem

What is a Polifonia Ecosystem *component*?

Basically, anything that is not a research paper, dissemination product (e.g., video presentation of a tool), or deliverable.

List of component types:

Documentation:

- Persona (strictly from <https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>)
- Story (strictly from <https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>)
- Tutorial
- Documentation

Executables:

- Application
- Container
- Experiment
- CLI tool

Reusable software:

- Library
- User Interface
- Service

Data:

- Registry
- Ontology

- Dataset
- Repository
- Corpus
- Knowledge Graph

Polifonia Ecosystem Website

A repository contains the development work for at least 1 component in the **Polifonia Ecosystem**. One markdown text file should expose annotations (metadata) relative to a single component included in the repository. For example, a component-name.md file using the annotation schema of the Polifonia Ecosystem (the file can have any name). A repository can include multiple annotated files, hence expose multiple components. Those annotations will be used by the [Polifonia Ecosystem website](#). This website will provide a user interface for navigating through the Polifonia Ecosystem (with aggregation pages, tags, etc). Please note that the Polifonia ecosystem website uses the content of Github repositories as is, hence the need for good quality annotations / documentation.

Developing Schema Components Annotations

The annotations should be written at the top of the markdown file, between 2 "---" lines. The markup format is YAML (mostly a "key: value" format, see also example at the top of this file). The schema to follow is [this one](#). Developers can use this service to test the YAML code: <https://jsonformatter.org/yaml-validator>.

Process towards ecosystem releases

- Champions curate releases with project-specific frequency and rationale
 - Releases must be linked to Zenodo and the related Polifonia Community
- TB calls for next Ecosystem Release
- Champions reply giving details about version number and expected deadline (if any)
- Champions ensure component metadata is accurate
- Ecosystem Website prepare release candidate
- TB tests and validates Ecosystem Website release candidate
- Ecosystem released

How to contribute to the Rulebook

Please open an issue with proposals or questions about the rulebook!

2.3.2.4.2. Current version of the Ecosystem Component Annotation Schema (as part of the Ecosystem rulebook)²⁷

Ecosystem Component Annotation Schema

Use the schema

Just copy the YAML code below and use it as the header of your component description MD file.

```
---
component-id:
name:
description:
type:
release-date:
release-number:
work-package:
pilot:
keywords:
  - kw1
  - kw2
changelog:
licence:
release link:
image:
logo:
demo:
links:
  - link
running-instance:
credits:
related-components:
  - component-id-1
  - component-id-2
bibliography:
  - oneref
  - another ref
---
```

²⁷ <https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook/blob/main/schema.md> Version September 30,2022

See below for a description of the fields and expected values.

Description of fields

Name	Description	Format/Example
component-id	Identifier of the component	lowercase
name	Full name of the component	Text (no size limit)
description	A brief description of the component	100 word max.
type	Type of component	one of: Tutorial, Documentation, Application, Container, Experiment, CLI, Library, User, Interface, Service, Registry, Ontology, Dataset, Repository, Corpus, "Knowledge Graph"
release-date	Date of the release	2021-09-28 (ISO 8601)
release-link	Link to the release	https://github.com/SPARQL-Anything/sparql.anything/releases/tag/v0.5.1
release-number	Version number for the current release	v0.1
work-package	Relevant WPs (list)	[WP ₁ , WP ₂]
pilot	Pilot identifiers	[FACETS, TUNES]
keywords	List of keywords (max 8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● keyword₁● keyword₂● ...
changelog	Link to a document specifying the changes between this and the previous version	URL

licence	A licence for the code	MIT, GPLv3. A link may be provided: Unlicense
release-link	A link towards a release archive/image	URL
image	A presentation image (JPEG, PNG, etc.)	URL
logo	A logo for the component (JPEG, PNG, etc.)	URL
demo	A demonstration for the component (e.g., video tutorial)	A link for the demo
links	A list of relevant web links	List of URLs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://onelink.com • http://www.anotherone.com
running-instance	A link towards a running instance of the component	URL
credits	Names of people participating in the development	E. Daga (OU), R. Fournier-S'niehotta (CNAM)
related-components	Relevant components	[component-id1, component-id2, ...]
bibliography	Relevant publications	List of references

Information that can be automatically derived

- Statistics such as number of commits
- Contributors (number of them or list of them)
- Creation date
- Number of releases
- Size

- Programming language
- Link to repository, issues, etc ...
- Citat

2.3.2.5. Technical Board

The Ecosystem is not a once and for ever fixed outcome, but - as the name suggests - a living instrument whose parts are adapted to the needs of Polifonia during its lifetime. That means that the Classification Structure (Components) of the Ecosystem²⁸, the Annotation scheme (see previous section 2.3.2.4.2), and the Rulebook (see previous section 2.3.2.4.1.) are living documents too. The Technical Board, which meets monthly, is the governing body of Polifonia to discuss and decide about such changes. "Technical Board (TB), composed of representative members of the partners expecting to contribute to the development of the technical outputs of the project. The role of the TB is to support the coordination of the technical activities and facilitate the interaction and collaboration. In particular, the TB monitors technical developments fostering the sharing of expertise with the objective of maximising reuse of knowledge, skills, and resources. Members of the TB are responsible for ensuring the quality of the technical outputs, both from the point of view of good practices of software engineering and from the perspective of providing guidance and support to developers in curating documentation, tutorials, and user guides. In addition, the TB supervises the curation of resources for developers, so as to maximise the reuse of the outputs by third-party organisations of the cultural heritage sector and industry." (Daga et al. 2022). A Technical Director (Enrico Daga) coordinates the TB, which currently consists of 8 members, representing all pilots, and WP's and the Data Steward.

2.3.3. The Polifonia Portal

The Polifonia portal is designed to enable interaction between users and resources provided by members of the Polifonia consortium and produced during the Polifonia project itself. It is currently in the design phase and the first deliverable on it is scheduled for June 2023. It contains both sources and information retrieval tools to navigate them; and dashboards (information analysis for envisioned user needs). What users can do with the resources will slightly differ, but the aim is to serve different user groups (from lay experts, wider public, and domain experts). Moreover, users will also be empowered to come with their own resources and use the tooling the Portal provides. In designing the access, licences coming with data are essential and need to be obliged and communicated. In essence, all data that are served via the web portal are Linked Open Data. As the name says, these are data released with an open license (public domain or more likely CC-BY 4.0). The sources of such data are not released by Polifonia, since these, in most cases, are already available online with their own licensing restrictions (open enough to allow us to do knowledge extraction). An example of the complexity of this situation is the Polifonia corpus, whose original documents cannot be re-published (see <https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Corpus>).

The Polifonia portal represents the 'out-side' looking face of the project. It builds on components which are part of the Polifonia Ecosystem and have been developed in the Polifonia Github instance.

Figure 8 displays the different components of the portal as envision at September 2022

²⁸ <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/polifonia-project/rulebook/README.html>

Figure 8: Schematic overview of the components of the Polifonia Portal (source, presentation at the Polifonia consortium meeting Paris, 2022, courtesy of Marilena Daquino)

Parts 1-2-3 in the above figure stand for the data backbone of the Portal. In part 1 data sources are catalogued (using the musoW platform). Together with the application CLEF (Crowdsourcing Linked Entities via web Form) and a music recommender (under development) the catalogue will be enriched with new data sources. Part 2 entails the Dashboard interface (called Melody) which enables expert users to engage with the data. Part 3 concerns means to disseminate and entertain wider audiences and is the part still most under construction. The Portal runs on OS: Linux, with a storage of 2-3 TB and will serve <100GB Medium size datasets, stored in dedicated triplestores and served via SPARQL endpoint/Web API (open).

All software products used for the portal are developed and shared in Github, and selectively entered and annotated in the Polifonia Ecosystem. Backups in Zenodo are made whenever appropriate. The University of Bologna hosts the server behind the portal, and guarantees its maintenance for five years after the project.

All data representations will be in Linked Open Data, obliging the Polifonia Ontology Network model and contributing to the Polifonia Knowledge Graph.

2.4. Data Security

2.4.1. Polifonia Zenodo Community

The paradigm of Polifonia is to work with and produce open data, but at the same time also to comply with GDPR where necessary (see ACCESS pilot as an example, where live sessions with participants will be recorded). The responsibility for Data Security lies in principle with the consortium members. Having said this, Polifonia's outcome is documented in a Polifonia Github instance (most repositories are public),

and/or in the Polifonia Zenodo Community²⁹. Polifonia agreed to use Zenodo as general repository for various forms of output behind of what constitutes the Polifonia Portal and Polifonia Ecosystem: from software products and data collections (as produced in GitHub repositories) to typical research output such as presentations, publications, data sets, all project deliverables and so on.

In Zenodo, a Polifonia community was created (2021). Creating a community in Zenodo entails to apply a moderator, which checks and, if needed, curates content submitted via the community. Currently, WP6 provides the Zenodo community curator.³⁰ In turn, we make sure that all relevant output can be found under one umbrella. **Upload guidelines** are produced and regularly updated to ensure good quality submissions and good quality metadata. The most recent Polifonia Zenodo Upload Guide can be found in the next subsection 2.4.1.1.

In future, we will focus on completeness, quality of metadata, and automatic submission (from GitHub to Zenodo) of output of Polifonia. We will also analyse how Polifonia appears in the OpenAire Dashboard³¹ which harvests from Zenodo.

2.4.1.1. Polifonia Zenodo Guidelines (version September 2022)

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge

Polifonia Zenodo Guidelines

Committed to scientific excellence and innovation, Polifonia has a growing number of project outputs. To collect and share the numerous Polifonia results and products, we'll use the dedicated community on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/polifonia/?page=1&size=20>) as an open-access repository. In this community, we aim to gather all the material produced by the Polifonia project such as all project deliverables, (preprints of) research papers, data sets (if not archived elsewhere), and research software (preferable via the Github based Polifonia Ecosystem). Submitting to the Polifonia Zenodo community helps to make the products of Polifonia visible also

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/polifonia/?page=1&size=20>

³⁰ Please note that a community can only have one moderator, which sometimes creates a bottleneck.

³¹ https://explore.openaire.eu/search/advanced/research-outcomes?fo=relprojectid&fvo=corda_h2020%253A%253A6fe14ofac4916d221fe12eb7cob1be39

at Dashboard such as OpenAire. Will you help us in collecting the Polifonia outputs in its dedicated platform?

Getting started:

1. Go to <https://zenodo.org/> or

<https://zenodo.org/login/?next=%2Fdeposit%2Fnew%3Fc%3Dpolifonia>

You will be asked to use an account you might have or to create one.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo login interface. At the top, it says "Log in to account". Below this are two buttons: "Log in with GitHub" and "Log in with ORCID". In the center, there is a separator "– OR –". Below the separator are two input fields: "Email Address" and "Password". The "Email Address" field has a user icon and a dropdown arrow. The "Password" field has a lock icon. Below the input fields is a blue "Log In" button. At the bottom, there is a link: "New to Zenodo? Sign Up".

2. Create an account if you need.

3. Click on 'Upload'

4. Drag & drop the file(s) to deposit.

How to fill the metadata fields of your Zenodo record when sharing your output?

Document metadata:

- Communities: Polifonia 2021-2024, playing the soundtrack of our history
<https://zenodo.org/communities/polifonia/?page=1&size=20>

- Upload type: There are several upload types, chose the appropriate, for Polifonia Deliverables choose: Publication -> Project Deliverable, unless you have a specific Publication type as a Data Management Plan or a software documentation or ...

In the following we demonstrate how to upload Deliverables. Please note that each type comes with slightly different metadata. Please fill them as complete as possible.

- DOI: leave it blank - except if you have already an DOI for the document, and want to point to this one. Think here of adding a pre-print version of an article, which has its own DOI.
- Publication date: the date on the Deliverable
 - Title: add the title of your contribution
For Deliverables it is usual the Deliverable name – don't forget to include the number DX.Y
 - Authors: add all authors **and their ORCIDs**
Check for ORCID numbers at <https://orcid.org>; *It would be good if the ORCID's would be already added to the Deliverables Template. There is an internal excel sheet which contains author names and ORCID of Polifonia members [HERE](#)*
 - Description: add a couple of sentences that will give an idea to your readers about the content of submission. Use an abstract if you have one. For Deliverables use the 'Executive summary'.
- Version: leave it blank until you add further versions. For Deliverables, use the version number of the Deliverable template
- Language: English
- Keywords: no specific suggestions
- Additional notes: optional
- Access: Open Access
- License: CC-BY 4.0 International [this is default in Zenodo]
- Funding: European Commission (EU) and **101004746** [the Polifonia connection will show up]
- Contributors: feel free to add any other persons you want to acknowledge and which are not already authors
- Related/alternative identifiers [read instruction on Zenodo]

Example of a record:

<https://zenodo.org/record/6963585#.YuvoPS8RphA>

If we collectively document nicely, our output is also nicely visible in an aggregated way here:

https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::6fe140fac4916d221fe12eb7c0b1be39

Should you have any questions, the Polifonia Dissemination team Marloes Bontje <mbontje@beeldengeluid.nl> and/or the Polifonia Data Stewards Rene van Horik <rene.van.horik@dans.knaw.nl>; Andrea Scharnhorst <andrea.scharnhorst@dans.knaw.nl> will be happy to help.

2.5. Ethical Aspects - Licences

To comply licences is important when operating on the paradigm of Open Source. Starting from the Survey (see section 2.1.1.) an overview about licences used by the pilots (their data sources) was produced in the framework of WP₁ (by Thomas Bottini, Achille Davy-Rigaux, Christophe Guillotel-Nothmann, Marco Gurrieri). The analysis produced an annotated list of copyrights (which is essential information who owns rights about an asset) and licences (as a set of guidelines how to use an asset). The licences and copyrights listed in the file concern mainly on-line music databases but also englobe most well-known Web resources (like Wikipedia).

The analysis resulted in a Google document "External datasets requests" ([living resource](#)³²), which contains currently two tabs: Tab 1: Licences/External databases and Tab 2: Licences and Characteristics. Tab1 contains column headers (Notes; Licence ID; Additional information; External datasets; Source of info about licence; copyright or accessibility; MusoW; Polifonia pilot) (see below for one row as an example)

Notes	Licence ID	Additional information	External datasets	Source of info about licence,	MusoW	Polifonia Pilot
-------	------------	------------------------	-------------------	-------------------------------	-------	-----------------

³² <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1cJ5oipaeJCibNVVgfX4sYMeEotiU6gGfea3bloF2TQU/edit#gid=0>

				copyright or accessibility		
	GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE, Version 3, 29 June 2007	copyright, free access	Gesualdo online	https://ricercar.gesualdo-online.cesr.univ-tours.fr/privacy	https://w3id.org/musow/1638949164-9532564	TONALITIES

Tab 2 contains column headers (Licence ID; URL; Share; Adapt; Attribution; Share Alike) (see below for one row)

LICENCE ID	URL	SHARE	ADAPT	ATTRIBUTION	SHARE ALIKE
CC BY-SA 3.0	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.	You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.	ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.

In Appendix 3: Overview on licences using in PILOTS and beyond - so-called file "External datasets requests", we display pdf versions (as image) of both Tabs (downloaded September 22, 2022). For close inspection, the recommendation is to read the on-line versions. The snapshots provide just an impression on the diversity of licences across the sources from whose Polifonia extracts information.

Currently, the work on collecting and analysing licences relevant for Polifonia is part of the Survey instance in Github. Eventually, information collected on licences will be described as Linked Open Data, and integrated into the Polifonia Knowledge Graph, and hence also become part of the Polifonia Ecosystem. (Task 2.4., M30). The current preparatory work (once turned into a machine-readable form) allows for analysis of licences currently in use in the Polifonia consortium, access possibilities for datasets and tools, and will eventually also guide Polifonia's own licence policy for Polifonia output.

2.6. Other Aspects - How do guidelines relate to each other?

2.6.1. Polifonia’s documentation strategy: platforms

As already introduced in the *Allocation of Resources* section, Polifonia uses different platforms to carefully document its research process and output, and has developed guidelines for all of them. Most notably platforms used are:

- The POLIFONIA ECOSYSTEM which is documented and moderated in Polifonia GitHub instance according to -> **Rulebook for the Ecosystem**
- ZENODO (for all Deliverables, presentations, papers (or author-copies/preprints of papers, but also releases of the GitHub-based Polifonia: Ecosystem) -> **Guide how to upload into the Polifonia Zenodo community**
- The POLIFONIA PORTAL which is interface to resources hosted elsewhere as well as hosts resources itself

Additionally, Polifonia uses a Sharepoint instance provided by UNIBO for internal documentation and file exchange. This instance is not public. The liveunibo.sharepoint instance enables the day-to-day coordination of the project, reporting, exchange of presentations, note taking for all meetings, etc.

Figure 9 shows pipelines of documentation

Figure 9: Polifonia Platforms, their functions and how content is submitted

The various guidelines connect and reinforce each other.

The Polifonia Knowledge Graph (and all operations possible due to this graph) forms the centre of reference.

2.6.2. Interdependencies of guidelines

The following list summarises current practices, and shows the interdependencies of guidelines:

- All publications of Linked (Open) Data follow the PON and become part of the PKG. Rules, licences, annotation schemes are equally integrated in the PON and PKG. (WP2 guides this work)
- All data and tool development activities take place in the Polifonia GitHub instance, monitored by the Technical Board. Cornerstones of the development selected as Components of the Polifonia Ecosystem will be annotated according to the **rulebook**.
- Specific attention is given to software development in the course of research. This specific type of an Ecosystem component (and type of a deliverable) has to oblige the Polifonia Deliverable Guidelines, which are a specification of the rulebook. For reviewers of such deliverables a check-list has been developed.
- In Zenodo, a Polifonia community has been established. Automatic release workflows of GitHub repositories into Zenodo are used, combined with metadata enhancement according to the Polifonia Zenodo Upload Guidelines. Those guidelines also apply to any other output registration in Zenodo - which is mandatory for Deliverables, Publications and main presentations.
- Any (bibliographical) documentation independent of the platform used for it, will comply with the Polifonia Open Science Rules. This concerns in particular the use of Persistent Identifiers (PID) and FAIR principles in Linked Data Production.
- All guidelines will be periodically reviewed by the Technical Board and updated.

Figure 10 gives a Q/A overview on how to deal with the rules.

What do I do?	How do I do it?
Develop software or provide data for Polifonia in the course of research	Use the Polifonia Github instance to document your work
Provide software/data for the Polifonia Ecosystem	Annotate your components according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook
Produce a software deliverable for Polifonia	Use the Software checklist
Publish content as Linked Data	Re-use and align with the Polifonia Ontology Network and Polifonia Knowledge Graph; consult information about licences; bring problems to the Technical Board
Upload output to Zenodo (either manually or automatically)	Follow the Polifonia Zenodo Upload guidelines
For all documentation purposes (Github or Zenodo or elsewhere)	Follow the Polifonia Open Science Rules
Looking for a server to deploy my Linked Data	Follow the Knowledge Graph provider rules (and the internal rules of how to use the Polifonia server)

Figure 10: Overview which guides to follow

3. Outlook - How to further improve data management in Polifonia? - Towards the DMP version 3

As explained in the introduction data management is an inherent part of the coordination of the Polifonia project. Polifonia is now in a phase where all platforms where results of Polifonia are produced, documented and made available for interaction and use are in place. For each of those platforms and for many relevant workflows, rules/guides have been developed. In the coming months challenges are:

- to check for the good implementation of all rules
- to explore if those guidelines can be further aligned or even combined
- to monitor where guidelines and rules need to be adapted due to new insights, insights both from the general FAIR discourse as well as from the experiences to work with them in Polifonia
- to check if 'score systems' to indicate FAIRness can be implemented
- to use harvesters and overview tools such as the Polifonia Ecosystem website, and the OpenAire explorer to showcase the dynamic output of the project, and to make interlinks and dependencies better visible
- to further clarify the situation of around IRP and licences. The work documented in section 2.5. will be incorporated into a Knowledge Graph of licences. As part of the Polifonia Knowledge Graph this will also clarify which data sources can be used by machines for which processes. We expect that this leads to a further sharpening of the Polifonia Open Science Rule #9.

This will be done by the following means

1. Continue and further strengthen the "data steward" role in the project³³
 - a. Participation in the Technical Board (ongoing) (including the further alignment of rules)
 - b. Consultations prior to Deliverable submission, in particular concerning the FAIR Protocol
 - c. Participation in cross WP meetings (weekly, bi-weekly)
2. Create a working group on data curation of Zenodo content (with WP6) (November 2022)
 - a. Check for metadata content consistency
 - b. Make sure all content in Zenodo is linked to the Polifonia community
3. Review the rulebook and components annotation metadata scheme (from January 2022 onwards) in the Technical Board
 - a. make sure that all other guidelines are represented
4. Put licences and licence policy on the agenda of the Technical Board. Organise a workshop or webinar around it.

³³ For an overview of the required skills and competences, see: <https://moodle.learn.eosc-synergy.eu/course/view.php?id=132> and <https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/training>

The Polifonia DMP version 3 (due M30) will contain updated versions of guides and tables. It will also entail a reflection and concrete measures concerning the long-term sustainability of Polifonia's contributions.

Appendix 1: Overview of the main sources used in the pilots

(updated September 2022, additions columns, rows, content are colour coded in red)

	Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
1	BELLS	over all sources			XML, RDF, MAG and other formats	ArCo, Unimarc ICCD Vocabulary for Musical Instruments ICCD Vocabulary for Intangible Heritage	JPEG, TIFF, XML, RDF, HTML, MP3, various sound formats			API SPARQL (customizable query). For photographs we have API IIF (Internationale Image Interoperability Framework)
		General Catalogue of Cultural Assets	https://catalogo.beniculturali.it					open	CC BY-SA 4.0 (data and content)	

³⁴ Source: Survey ([GitHub](#))

³⁵ Source: Licence overview ([working document](#)), licences and copyright as indicated by the data providers

³⁶ Source: Inventory Knowledge Graph providers Working group ([internal](#))

Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶	
	Portale dei dati aperti del MiC	dati.cultura.gov.it Linked Open Data del MIC			Ar.Co		Open	CC BY-SA 4.0 (data and content)		
	Patrimonio Culturale Immateriale (catalogue sheets)	http://paci.iccd.beniculturali.it/iccd/cards/ricercaPaci?data%5Bkeyword%5D=tecnica+campanaria&data%5BricercaLiberalInventario%5D=Cerca&data%5Bdoaction%5D=cerca					open	CC BY-SA 4.0 (data and content)		
	Campanologia.it	https://www.campanologia.it/				html	open	copyright		
	Campane.org	http://www.campane.org/				html	open	copyright		
	Linee guida per la tutela del Patrimonio Campanario	http://www.archeobologna.beniculturali.it/pdf/Protocollo%20di%20Intesa_Patrimonio%20Campanario%20Storico.pdf	8,2 MB			pdf	open	copyright author	N/A	
	The Bell Ontology module; Part of POLIFONIA Github	https://github.com/polifonia-project/bell-ontology	two datasets a 68 triples	ArCo Ontology network		RDF	Open	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/	in development ³⁷	
2	ORGANS	Het Historische Orgel in Nederland (1997-2010)	https://vu.on.worldcat.org/oclc/782207831	60 MB	Thesaurus of organ terms exists	Possible connection to KOS for musical instruments.	doc, docx, WP5	restricted	copyright NiVO ³⁸	not yet, but exploration of

³⁷ Published on a platform of a consortium member, some few datasets might need hosting on the central Polifonia server

³⁸ <https://nationaalinstituutorgelkunst.nl/en/goal-and-mission>

Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
					Probably, design one specifically for texts about (historical) pipe organs.				hosting with third parties such as Muziek web (national audio archive - all music (CDs) issued on Dutch market) - Muziek bibliotheek van de omroep (National Broadcast Music Library)
ORGANS	LOD publication	https://github.com/polifonia-project/organs-dataset	11,5 MB	PON	PON+	html, ttl	private	see above	to be integrated into Portal

	Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
3	FACETS	Neuma digital library	http://neuma.humanum.fr/		MIDI ontology? envisioned: PON	MEI, MusicXML	MIDI, MusicXML, MEI, ly, png, pdf	registered users/open		Yes, fully, through a REST API. http://neuma.humanum.fr/home/services
		Irish Traditional Music Archive (Port collections)	http://port.itma.ie/welcome							
4	INTERLINK	across all sources			TXT, MIDI, Filemaker, CSV, XML	MusicXML, MEI, MARC-XML, LY, JAMS MIDI ontologies, MIDI instrument taxonomies	TAR, GZIP, RDF, N-triples, RDF, RDFS, OWL, Filemaker, KERN, MIDI, PDF, TXT, JSON, PNG, MXL, ABC, MEI, SQL databases, CSV, TSV, HTML, HARM, JSON, JAMS, etc.			http://grlc.io/api/midid/queries/
4	INTERLINK	Dutch Song Database	www.liederenbank.nl	630 MB	Filemaker Database		Filemaker Database	open	https://www.meertens.knaw.nl/cms/nl/over-het-meertens-instituut/disclaimer	no
		MTC-FS-INST-2.0	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	1.3 GB	csv		**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no
		MTC-ANN-2.0.1	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	84 MB	csv		**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no

	Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
		Melodic Features for Meertens Tune Collections and ESSEN Folksong Collection	https://zenodo.org/record/3551003	81.6 MB	N/A		json	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no
		Stichting Omroep Muziek catalogue	http://muziekschatten.nl							
		Musopen	https://musopen.org/							
		CLARIAH MediaSuite	https://mediasuite.clariah.nl/							
		Common Thesaurus for Audiovisual Archives	https://old.datahub.io/dataset/ge-meenschappelijke-thesaurus-audiovisuele-archieven							
		Neuma digital library	http://neuma.humanum.fr/				MusicXML MEI, ly, png,pdf	registered users		yes
		Irish Traditional Music Archive (Port collections)	http://port.itma.ie/welcome							
		Irish Traditional Music Archive (LITMUS)	https://www.itma.ie/litmus							
		RISM Catalog of Musical Sources	https://rism.info	6.4 GB	XML		MARC-XML, RDF	open	CC-BY	no
5	CHILD	Listening Experience Database	https://led.kmi.open.ac.uk	12161 datasets (listening)	RDF	Bibo (bibliographic ontology)	RDF	open	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/	https://data.open.ac.uk/index

	Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
				experiences		Dublin Core metadata terms FOAF The Music Ontology The Event Ontology by Yves Raimond and Samer Abdallah OWL-Time Schema.org (provisional, but could be confirmed) DBpedia ontology 3.9 (to be superseded)				php?path=sparql
		Internet Archive	https://archive.org							
		Project Gutenberg	https://www.gutenberg.org							
6	MUSIBO				Relational database; RDF	n/a	CSV, TSV			Yes
6	MUSICBO	Lessico Beni Culturali	http://corpora.lessicobeniculturali.net/						CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	
		Grove Online Dictionary	https://www.oxfordmusiconline.com/					registered users	copyright Oxford University Press	no

	Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ⁴⁵	File format(s) ⁴⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
		Retrospective Index to Music Periodicals	https://www.ripm.org/?page=ROAoverview							
		Internet Archive Open Library	https://openlibrary.org/							
		Gallica	https://gallica.bnf.fr							
		Biblioteca Universitaria di Bologna	https://bub.unibo.it/it/bub-digitale							
		Biblioteca della Musica	http://www.bibliotecamusica.it/cmbm/scripts/gaspari/src_com.asp							
		Biblioteca Conservatorio P. Martini	http://www.consbo.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/23							
		Bibliothèque Nationale	https://www.bnf.fr/fr/acces-aux-catalogues-numerises							
		Biblioteca Nacional España	http://www.bne.es/es/Catalogos/BibliotecaDigitalHispanica/Inicio/index.html							
7	TUNES				MusicXML, MEI, MARC-XML, Essen associative code, ABC, HUMDRUM, LY, KERN	CSV, Filemaker, XML, TXT, HTML	MIDI, PDF, PNG, JPG, TXT, MP3, Filemaker, JSON, HTML			
7	TUNES	Dutch Song Database	www.liederenbank.nl	630 MB	Filemaker Database		Filemaker Database,	open	https://www.meerte.nl/knaw.nl/cms/nl/ov	no

Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
								er-het-meertens-instituut/disclaimer	
	MTC-FS-INST-2.0	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	1.3 GB	csv		**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no
	MTC-ANN-2.0.1	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	84 MB	csv		**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no
	Melodic Features for Meertens Tune Collections and ESSEN Folksong Collection	https://zenodo.org/record/3551003	81.6 MB	N/A		json	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no
	Neuma digital library	http://neuma.humanum.fr/				MusicXML, MEI, ly, png, pdf	registered users		yes
	Irish Traditional Music Archive (Port collections)	http://port.itma.ie/welcome							
	RISM Catalog of Musical Sources	https://rism.info	6.4 GB	XML		MARC-XML, RDF	open	CC-BY	no
	Essen Folk Song Collection	http://www.esac-data.org/		txt		txt (ascii) : Essen associative code	open		no
	Tune index from The Colonial Institute	https://www.cdss.org/elibrary/Easmes/Index.htm	11 MB	HTML		txt (ascii) : HTML	open		no
	Barlow and Morgenstern Collection	https://onsearch.library.uwa.edu.au/permalink/61UWA_INST/11ju3hj/alm9998597202101	51 MB	N/A		txt (ascii) : **kern	open		no

Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
	ABC notation	http://abcnotation.com/	unknown	txt		txt (ascii) : abc encoding	open		no
8	TONALITIES			OWL, CIDOC-CRM, CRMdig, LRMoo, DCTERMS, MEI	<p>Analysis ontology: https://github.com/polifonia-project/modal-tonal-ontology/blob/main/analysisOntology.rdfModal-tonal ontologies:</p> <p>Zarlino 1558: https://github.com/polifonia-project/modal-tonal-ontology/blob/main/historicalModels/modalityTonality_Zarlino_1558.rdf</p> <p>Praetorius 1619 https://github.com/polifonia-project/modal-tonal-ontology/blob/main/historicalModels/modalityTonality_Praetorius_1619.owl</p> <p>Music21: https://github.com/polifonia-project/modal-</p>	RDF		Various, see for details https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1C5oipaeJCibNVVgfX4sYMeEotiU6gGfa3bloF2TQU/edit-gid=0	Yes, SPARQL

	Pilot	Source	Link/reference	File size	Metadata model/ format ³⁴	Metadata standards ³⁵	File format(s) ³⁵	Access rights	Licence/ copyright ³⁵	API ³⁶
						tonal-ontology/blob/main/otherModels/music21.rdf				
8	TONALITIES	NEUMA	http://neuma.humanum.fr/				MusicXML, MEI, ly, png, pdf	registered users		yes
		Dutch Song Database	www.liederenbank.nl	630 MB	Filemaker Database		Filemaker Database	open	https://www.meertens.knaw.nl/cms/nl/over-het-meertens-instituut/disclaimer	no
		MTC-FS-INST-2.0	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	1.3 GB	csv		**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no
		MTC-ANN-2.0.1	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	84 MB	csv		**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no
		Melodic Features for Meertens Tune Collections and ESSEN Folksong Collection	https://zenodo.org/record/3551003	81.6 MB	N/A		json	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no
9	ACCESS	Live and recorded performances at The Stables Theatre								
10	MEETUPS	Listening Experience Database: https://led.kmi.open.ac.uk	see above CHILD				RDF			
		Internet Archive	https://archive.org							
		Project Gutenberg	https://www.gutenberg.org							
		Biblioteca Italiana	http://www.bibliotecaitaliana.it							
		BNF France	https://www.bnf.fr/en/bibliotheque-nationale-de-france-catalogue-general							

Appendix 2: FAIR Protocol section in Deliverables

Mail of the coordinator

From: Valentina Presutti <valentina.presutti@unibo.it>
Date: Thursday, 9 June 2022 at 13:23
To: Polifonia <polifonia@live.unibo.it>
Subject: Section on FAIR protocol to be included in all deliverables

Dear all,

the DMP team is working towards providing us clear and short guidelines on how to handle data management (I'd say our products' management) in a FAIR way. These will be presented during our plenary meeting in September and then a template will be provided to be included in all future deliverables.

Nevertheless, to help them defining this template and collecting information about how we are addressing the FAIRness principles, I ask all deliverable editors and authors to include a section at the end of the report with the following content:

Title: FAIR protocol

- summarise with a list all components released as result of the work described in the report (this will be redundant but yet it's useful to have a bullet list with links all in one place) [consult Polifonia 10 Rules of Open Science, Rule 8]
- describe the practice and tools implemented to make them FAIR [Rule 8]
- strategy for long-term persistence

Andrea and Rene are available for quick advice chats - there's a new channel on discord #fair-and-dmp dedicated to this issue

They also will review your draft section before submission if you ask them.

Thanks for your collaboration.

Kind regards,
Valentina

FAIR Protocol sections

D1.2 Roadmap and pilot requirements 2nd version

Guillotel-Nothmann et al. 2022

“FAIR protocol

The following components have been released as a direct or indirect result of the work described in this deliverable:

1. Ecosystem
2. Web portal
3. XD-UX methodology related data
4. Survey
5. Validation framework

Via Github, all components – or in the case of the XD-UX-design methodology their outcomes (i.e. the Personas, Stories and CQ) – have a unique and persistent identifier and are registered in a searchable resource. The Survey, in its current version, has also been deposited in Zenodo⁵⁹. All the components have been described with and/or contribute to produce rich metadata: The Ecosystem is targeted towards producing metadata through its annotation schema; all resources of the Web portal are provided with metadata (scope, audience, type of data served, data access points)⁶⁰.

Finally, as components of the Ecosystem, the Survey and the Validation framework are described with metadata defining their type, contents, and relation to the WPs. This also applies to the outcomes of the XD-UX-design methodology. The storage of all resources on Github and on Zenodo (in the case of the Survey) guarantees their persistence beyond the project.

Since all components and their related data benefit from the Ecosystem annotation schema (and are registered in Zenodo in the case of the Survey), they are all retrievable by their identifier using standardised communications protocols. These protocols are open, free, and universally implementable. Furthermore, the Ecosystem infrastructure with its annotation schema is independent of its individual components. Therefore, the metadata remains accessible, even if the data is no longer available.

All data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. The resources disseminated by the Web portal are made available in the form of RDF triples from the PKG. The Survey data will also eventually be transformed into an RDF knowledge graph (the PiKG). The resources created by the XD-UX design methodology through the Persona, Stories and CQ are all open linked data of the PON. As for the Ecosystem and Validation framework, their organisation is made explicit by the Ecosystem annotation scheme.

Finally, the Ecosystem, the Survey, the Stories which are derived from the XD-UX-design

methodology, and the Validation framework are released with a CC–BY 4.0 licence that allows all resources to be copied and redistributed in any medium or format. The material may also be remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose, even commercially. The different resources of the Web portal are released under CCo and ISC licences.

⁵⁹ Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, Gurrieri, Marco, van Kranenburg, Peter, Musumeci, Elena, Veninata, Chiara, Berardinis, Jacopo de, Fournier-S'niehotta, Raphaël, Marzi, Eleonora, Barlow, Helen, Daga, Enrico, & Holland, Simon. (2022). Polifonia Survey (Version 19062022) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6664200>.

⁶⁰ Furthermore, it is planned to develop a dedicated pipeline for data enrichment for case the metadata would be incomplete.

D1.9: Polifonia Web portal - 1st version (V1.0)

Daquino et al. 2022

“5.1 Reusability of results

musoW is currently used by scholars in Polifonia and outside the consortium to explore the landscape of music heritage on the web. Stakeholders include also professionals, like music journalists and music librarians (already engaged in the design of the registry). CLEF is of interest to a broad community, especially to those scholars or institutions that cannot afford commercial products or that do not have technical skills in house to deploy complex systems. Such a scenario is common in the Cultural Heritage domain. Likewise, the dashboarding system fills in a gap in the state of art for LOD exploratory analysis and storytelling, and it is highly reusable with any kind of Linked Data. Currently, only users of the Polifonia project can access it. In the near future we will open up the possibility to use the software to all users with a github account, granting the possibility to publish for free their stories on a dedicated repository as static web pages. Potentially, CLEF and MELODY can be combined to provide a comprehensive solution to handle the life-cycle of LOD - from creation, to publication, exploration and preservation. The pipeline for populating musoW can be used as-is, regardless of the actual interaction with musoW, to create newsletters. While its reuse on different scopes is not planned, developers can reuse our approach to develop similar pipelines and create their own recommender.”

D2.4: Methods for interlinking knowledge graphs (V1.0)

Meroño Peñuela et al. 2022

“5 FAIR Protocol

The following outputs have been released as a result of the work described in this deliverable:

1. ChoCo Knowledge Graph (ChoCo-KG) dataset¹
2. MIDI2vec algorithm²
3. MIDI2vec edgelists and learned embeddings³

We have implemented a number of actions to ensure that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [142]. In particular,

via GitHub the both the ChoCo dataset and the MIDI2vec algorithm's source code have a unique and persistent identifier and is registered in a searchable source. Additionally, all MIDI2vec experiments are available as notebooks at <https://git.io/midi-embs>. The data produced by the MIDI2vec algorithm (edgelist and learned embeddings) is available as a Zenodo deposit at <https://zenodo.org/record/5082300>. Once ChoCo is published through an ongoing paper in progress, we will deposit the dataset in Zenodo and publish its stable URL in GitHub. Through the addition of YAML metadata according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook⁴ [2], the ChoCo dataset and MIDI2vec algorithm are integrated within the Ecosystem automatically through its future releases with well-described, machine-processable metadata from various interoperable schemas. The storage of all resources on Github guarantees their persistence beyond the project. Additionally, we plan on adding to ChoCo and MIDI2vec fine-grained provenance descriptions, using standards for interoperable provenance representations, such as PROV [143], to the transformation processes we apply to ChoCo source datasets, and the representations of MIDI files. This is especially relevant to the issue of data authority, since the original data both approaches rely on were made available by other persons and institutions outside Polifonia.

Being integrated as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem, all data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. The resources created by the ChoCo dataset are themselves released as an RDF Knowledge Graph, making such resources uniquely identifiable to a fine-grained level, findable through the Web Portal, accessible through e.g. SPARQL queries, interoperable via the aforementioned vocabularies, and reusable via open source licenses. Because of this very nature, the ChoCo dataset will be also straightforwardly integrated in the Web Portal.

Finally, MIDI2vec is released with a CC-BY 4.0 licence that allows all resources to be copied and redistributed in any medium or format. The material may also be remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose, even commercially. We are investigating the complexities of licensing ChoCo content, as the dataset relies on the various licenses of the original partitions; for now we are including these in the aforementioned provenance representations.

¹[GitHub URL is upcoming upon the dataset's release.](#)

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/midi2vec>

³<https://zenodo.org/record/5082300>

⁴<https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>"

D2.7: Ontology testing and evaluation report; knowledge graph documentation and access interfaces (V1.0)

Meroño Peñuela et al., 2022a

“FAIR Protocol

The following outputs have been released as a result of the work described in this deliverable:

1. XDTesting infrastructure¹.

We have implemented a number of actions to ensure that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [23]. In particular, via GitHub the XDTesting infrastructure has a unique and persistent identifier and is registered in a searchable source. Through the addition of YAML metadata according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook² [1], the XDTesting infrastructure will be integrated within the Ecosystem automatically through its future releases with well-described, machine-processable metadata from various interoperable schemas. The storage of all resources on Github guarantees their persistence beyond the project. Additionally, the very architecture of XDTesting relies on GitHub actions, which can be seen as provenance execution traces—a possible mapping of these actions into interoperable provenance representations, such as PROV [24], is planned for the future. Being integrated as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem, all data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. The resources created by the XDTesting framework will be released in the future as an RDF knowledge graph.

Finally, XDTesting is released with a CC-BY 4.0 licence that allows all resources to be copied and redistributed in any medium or format. The material may also be remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose, even commercially.

¹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/XD-Testing>

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>

D3.3: Software Tools for Mining Patterns in Music Repositories (V1.0)

Diamond et al. 2022

“FAIR protocol

In this chapter we describe the approach to the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles in respect of the software components of this deliverable. The Netherlands eScience Center and DANS recommend the following five action items for FAIR software¹:

- Use a publicly accessible repository with version control *Done* (GitHub)
- Add a license *Done* (CC-BY 4)
- Register your code in a community repository *Done* (Zenodo)
- Enable citation of the software *Done* (bibtex citation in README.md)
- Use a software quality checklist *Done* during deliverable review².

Details on the two components’ FAIR aspects are below.

FONN - FOlk N-gram aNalysis https://github.com/polifonia-project/folk_ngram_analysis. In accordance with common open-source practice we have developed the FONN tools software in the open, in GitHub. GitHub provides findability and accessibility. We have written the code in Python, using a common music information retrieval library (MIR) (Music21), which ensures compatibility with many other pieces of software in related fields. It also ensures that authors and researchers face few obstacles in learning from or contributing to our software. Both input data and output data are stored in standardised, documented, common formats with certainty of long-term accessibility, including csv and the Python pickle format (<https://docs.python.org/3/library/pickle.html>). In particular, current results are stored in the corpus/ directory. Thus interoperability and reusability are ensured. GitHub itself provides long-term persistence. The software has also been archived on Zenodo for long-term persistence of the specific version reported here.

Root Note Detection https://github.com/polifonia-project/folk_ngram_analysis/tree/master/root_note_detection The comments above apply to the Root-note detection component also. One important difference is that here the outputs include not only data, but trained machine learning models. However, again the Python pickle format allows these to be saved to disk for reuse and persistence: they are stored in the root_note_detection/models directory. Reusability of these models by other researchers is simple, as documented in the demo notebook RootNoteDemo.ipynb.

¹<https://fair-software.eu/>

²The checklist is internal, but available to Polifonia members and on request: <https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/polifonia/Shared%20Documents/Deliverables/software-deliverable-checklist.docx?d=w15bea5d87fc34a1a812c8cad237aecbd&csf=1&web=1&e=45XBMC>

D4.2 : Interrogation and annotation of plurilingual corpora for discourse analysis (V1.0)

Tripodi et al. 2022

“FAIR Protocol

Our work in this chapter complies with the FAIR¹ principles and is in accordance with the Polifonia First Data Management Plan (D7.1).

The products released as a result of this work have been implemented following the FAIR data principles. The Polifonia Textual Corpus [1] data, metadata and statistics, along with its annotations and interrogation tools, are released under the CC BY license. We share the code that we used to construct, annotate and interrogate the corpus, along with the metadata of the corpus for findability and accessibility of its texts, through the dedicated Polifonia Corpus’ GitHub repository². The Polifonia Textual Corpus’ GitHub repository has been released on Zenodo³. Its

persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.67724534. The DOI ensures the long-term persistence of the resource. The royalty-free parts of the Polifonia Textual Corpus' data, metadata and annotations have been uploaded on Zenodo and are therefore publicly accessible for download (links are reported in Chapter 3 and Chapter 4). Data and annotations of the Polifonia Textual Corpus modules subject to heterogeneous licensing are only available to the Polifonia consortium members. Interested parties may contact us, and we will evaluate the sharing of the annotated data.

The practices implemented to ensure FAIRness of the products released as a result of the work described in this report are described in the list below:

- The Polifonia Textual Corpus. The central data used in this research served to develop the annotated Polifonia Textual Corpus [1] (cf. Chapter 3). Regarding the development of the Polifonia Textual Corpus, we reported its FAIRness and Reproducibility details in D4.1 [2]. We collected data from different sources (i.e. Wikipedia and open digital libraries with Creative Commons⁵ or similar licences⁶). The sources from which we downloaded the data allowed the non-commercial usage of their data. The texts obtained from digital libraries will not be shared publicly and will be used directly only by the Polifonia partners. The Polifonia Textual Corpus [1] data and metadata are hosted on public and private Zenodo repositories and therefore some of them are publicly accessible for download, others can be accessible only upon request. Links are reported in Chapter 3, Tables 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.8, 3.9.
- Annotations of the Polifonia Textual Corpus. For the annotation of the Polifonia Textual Corpus [1] (cf. Chapter 4) we used state-of-the-art Natural Language Processing technologies such as Spacy's⁷ trained pipelines (cf. Table 4.3); EWISER⁸; ARES⁹; WSD-games¹⁰; ExTenD¹¹. To ensure machine-readability and consistent encoding across different languages we decided to encode the annotations following an open standard, namely the CoNLL-U format¹², designed within the Universal Dependency (UD) project [24]. An example of a sentence of the Polifonia Textual Corpus [1], annotated and encoded following the CoNLL-U format, is shown in Table 4.1 in Chapter 4. The Polifonia Textual Corpus [1] annotations are hosted on public and private Zenodo repositories. The links of the public repositories are reported in Chapter 4, Tables 4.4.
- Interrogation of the annotated Polifonia Textual Corpus. We designed and implemented custom software interfaces (APIs) to ensure an effective interrogation of the annotated Polifonia Textual Corpus [1] to allow for performing structured queries on the corpus texts based on the annotations described in Chapter 4. Interrogation requirements have been collected by involving professors and senior researchers in the field of linguistics, as described in Section 5.1. We release the code to interrogate the corpus, along with detailed instructions to download the scripts and to satisfy its dependencies, in the dedicated section of the Polifonia Textual Corpus GitHub repository¹³.

The resources described in the bullet list above are part of the Polifonia Ecosystem¹⁴ and oblige the Ecosystem's Rulebook¹⁵. The Rulebook provides guidelines regarding how to track changes and progress issues, along with guidance regarding naming conventions, branches and releases. Compliance with the Rulebook guidelines on how to contribute to the Polifonia Ecosystem

ensures the sustainability of the resource by providing tools for documenting and monitoring strategies for medium and long-term maintenance.

As outlined in Chapter 6, the future work on the products released as a result of the work described in this report will focus on stimulating the engagement of the interested personas, especially by expanding the corpus interrogation APIs capabilities and by developing a User Interface to make the corpus interrogation more user-friendly. The data is a corpus, not a dataset in the terms of D7.1 Section 2.1.2, since it has not been converted to a Knowledge Graph or Linked Data format. However, this is envisaged as part of future work, as outlined in Section 6.3. No personal or sensitive information is involved in this strand of research, so there are no security or privacy concerns.

¹<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Corpus>

³<https://zenodo.org/>

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6772453>

⁵<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/it/deed.it>.

⁶<https://gallica.bnf.fr/edit/und/conditions-dutilisation-des-contenus-de-gallica>

⁷<https://spacy.io/>

⁸<https://github.com/SapienzaNLP/ewiser>

⁹<http://sensebert.org/>

¹⁰https://github.com/roccotrip/wsd_games_emb

¹¹<https://github.com/SapienzaNLP/extend>

¹²<https://universaldependencies.org/format.html>

Appendix 3: Overview on licences using in PILOTS and beyond - so-called file "External datasets requests"³⁹

Notes	Licence ID	Additional information	External datasets	Source of info about licence, copyright or accessibility	MusoW	Polifonia Pilot
	GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE, Version 3, 29 June 2007	copyright, free access	Gnuaido online	https://ricercar.gesualdo-online.cesar.univ-tours.fr/privacy	https://w3id.org/	TONALITIES
	GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE, Version 3, 29 June 2007	copyright, free access	CRIM (European side)	https://ricercar.crim.cesar.univ-tours.fr/privacy	https://w3id.org/	TONALITIES
	CC BY-NC 4.0	copyright, free access	CRIM (American side)	https://crimproject.org	https://w3id.org/	TONALITIES
	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	free access	Listening Experience Database	https://led.kmi.open.ac.uk/linkeddata/	https://w3id.org/	CHILD
	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	free access	Lessico Beni Culturali	http://corpora.lessicobeniculturali.net/it/		
	CC BY-SA 4.0	free access	Josquin project	https://github.com/josquin-research-project/jp-scores/commit/5742f86080bc89adba03a61c7807264b548b710		
	CC BY 3.0 US	free access	Measuring polyphony	https://github.com/MeasuringPolyphony/mp-music-files		
	CC BY-NC 3.0	copyright, free access	The Lost Voices project	http://digitalduchemin.org		
	Private (Meertens Institute)	copyright, free access	Dutch Song Database	https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:x/ri/sites/polifonia/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B3EC0372B-963D-439E-8619-EC60F1303B7B%7D&file=Annex%201.xlsx&action=default&mobiledirect=true		
	CC BY-SA 3.0	free access	Wikipedia	https://www.wikipedia.org		
	Apache License V 2.0, January 2004	free access	DBpedia	https://github.com/dbpedia/databus/commit/623030644b5e59f5e536051919fe20de3cb30b4d		
	GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE, Version 3, 29 June 2007	copyright, free access	Internet Archive.org	https://github.com/ijlaka/internetarchive/commit/ecb9e075f75e3504f30ce396779d0514230f19d6		
	GNU AFFERO GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE, Version 3, 19 November 2007			https://archive.org/about/terms.php		
	The Project Gutenberg Licence	copyright	Project Gutenberg	https://www.gutenberg.org/policy/license.html#section-1-general-terms-of-use-and-redistributing-project-gutenberg-tm-electronic-works		
	CC0 1.0+CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	free access	MusicBrainz	https://musicbrainz.org/doc/AboutData_License		
	CC0 1.0	copyright, free access	MIDI-D	https://www.dropbox.com/s/nyymwac5m4aav3/INTERLINK_externalDatasets.xlsx?dl=0		
	CC BY 4.0	copyright, free access	Lakh MIDI dataset	https://colinraffel.com/projects/lmd/#licensehttps://colinraffel.com/projects/lmd/copyrights.txt		
	CC BY-SA 4.0	free access	Catálogo Generale dei Beni Culturali	https://www.catalogo.beniculturali.it/termini-uso		
	CC BY-SA 4.0	free access	Patrimonio Culturale Immateriale (catalogue sheet)	https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:x/ri/sites/polifonia/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B3EC0372B-963D-439E-8619-EC60F1303B7B%7D&file=Annex%201.xlsx&action=default&mobiledirect=true		
	CC0 1.0	free access	Musopen	https://musopen.kmi.open.ac.uk/resources/8a0152fa0d162b410de71d7401c11881		
	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	free access	RISM Catalog of Musical Sources	https://rism.info/library_collections/2021/1/11/matteo-caprancia-a-composer-from-rieti.html		
	CC BY 4.0	copyright (partially), free access	Common Thesaurus for Audiovisual Archives	https://ahs.beahtengelvind.nl		
depends on the	CC BY-SA	free access	Neuma digital library	https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:x/ri/sites/polifonia/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B3EC0372B-963D-439E-8619-EC60F1303B7B%7D&file=Annex%201.xlsx&action=default&mobiledirect=true		
?	?	copyright	Campanologia.it			
not in MusoW	?	copyright	Campana.org			
?	?	copyright (not online)	Het Historische Orgel in Nederland (1997-2010)			
?	?	copyright, free access	Irish Traditional Music Archive (Pint collections)	https://musow.kmi.open.ac.uk/resources/9b0cd7258b2170c7aa25f53c62876b1		
?	?	copyright	Stichting Omroep Muziek catalogue	https://musow.kmi.open.ac.uk/resources/7a575537c4f73c0745b97df6564a702		
?	?	copyright, free access	CIARIM Media Suite	https://media.suite.clarim.nl/documentatie/nvaac-statement		
?	?	copyright	Irish Traditional Music Archive (ITMUS)	https://www.itma.ie/itmus/info		
?	?	copyright, fee-paying access	Grove Online Dictionary	https://www.oxfordmusiconline.com/grovemusic		
?	?	fee-paying access	Retrospective Index to Music Periodicals			
?	?	copyright, free access	Gallica	https://gallica.bnf.fr/ediit/und/conditions-utilisation-des-contenus-de-gallica		
?	?	free access	Biblioteca Universitaria di Bologna			
?	?	free access	Biblioteca della Musica			
?	?	free access	Biblioteca Conservatorio P. Martini			
?	?	free access	Bibliothèque Nationale de France			
?	?	free access	Biblioteca Nacional España			
?	?	free access	Essen Folk Song Collection	https://musow.kmi.open.ac.uk/resources/bd459503f11e71e0d23e83c32dc54b7		
?	?	copyright, free access	Tune Index from The Colonial Institute			
?	?	(not online)	Barlow and Morgenstern Collection			
?	?	copyright (partially), free access	ABC notation	https://abcnotation.com/searchCopyright		
?	?	copyright, free access	Marenzio Online	https://musow.kmi.open.ac.uk/resources/7034caef811242d4e1e911fe340625fehttp://www.marenzio.com/index.xhtml		
?	?	free access	Tasso in Music Project	https://musow.kmi.open.ac.uk/resources/786ad0983e6d233abd64e9cc6794160b		
?	?	copyright, free access	Genius	https://genius.com/static/copyright		
?	?	copyright, free access	SongFacts	https://www.songfacts.com/blog/pages/song-licensing		
?	?	copyright, free access	WhoSampled	https://www.whosampled.com/copyright/		
?	?	free access	MuseData	https://musow.kmi.open.ac.uk/resources/8014c3794d75c55c0e55b9888fa3c6e8		
?	?	copyright, free access	Early American Secular Music and Its European Sources, 1589–1839: An Index			
?	?	(not online)	Bach Chorales (Riemenschneider collection, 371 chorales)			
CC BY-NC-SA			Cantus Index	http://cantusindex.org/blog		
?		Canadian copyright laws	IMSLP	https://imslp.org/wiki/Main_Page		
?			Global chant			
?			Solovoces			
not all scores have	CPDL copyright license			https://www.cpdl.org/wiki/index.php/Help:What_copyright_rules_apply_to_CPDL_scores%3F		

LICENCE ID	URL	SHARE	ADAPT	ATTRIBUTION	SHARE ALIKE
GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE V3.0 (29 June 2007)	https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html	Everyone is permitted to copy and distribute verbatim copies of this license document	changing is not allowed		
GNU AFFERO GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE V3.0 (19 November 2007)	https://www.gnu.org/licenses/agpl-3.0.en.html	permission to copy, distribute and/or modify the software	You may convey a work based on the Program, or the modifications to produce it from the Program, in the form of source code under the terms of section 4, provided that you also meet all of these conditions:		
CC BY 3.0 US	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/us/	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.	You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.	
CC BY-SA 3.0	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.	You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.	ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.
CC BY-NC 3.0	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/3.0/deed.en_US	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for non commercial purposes	You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.	
CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for non commercial purposes	You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.	ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.
CC BY 4.0	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially		
CC BY-SA 4.0	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially	You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.	ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.
CC BY-NC 4.0	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for non commercial purposes	You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.	
CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/	copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format	remix, transform, and build upon the material for non commercial purposes	You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.	ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.
CC0 1.0	https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/	You can copy, modify, distribute and perform the work, even for commercial purposes, all without asking permission			
Apache License V 2.0, January 2004	http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0	perpetual, worldwide, non-exclusive, no-charge, royalty-free, irrevocable copyright license to reproduce, prepare Derivative Works of, publicly display, publicly perform, sublicense, and distribute the Work and such Derivative Works in Source or Object form.	You may reproduce and distribute copies of the Work or Derivative Works thereof in any medium, with or without modifications, and in Source or Object form, provided that You meet the following conditions: a/ You must give any other recipients of the Work or Derivative Works a copy of this License; and b/ You must cause any modified files to carry prominent notices stating that You changed the files; and c/ You must retain, in the Source form of any Derivative Works that You distribute, all copyright, patent, trademark, and attribution notices from the Source form of the Work, excluding those notices that do not pertain to any part of the Derivative Works; and d/ If the Work includes a "NOTICE" text file as part of its distribution, then any Derivative Works that You distribute must include a readable copy of the attribution notices contained within such NOTICE file, excluding those notices that do not pertain to any part of the Derivative Works, in at least one of the following places: within a NOTICE text file distributed as part of the Derivative Works; within the Source form or documentation, if provided along with the Derivative Works; or, within a display generated by the Derivative Works, if and wherever such third-party notices normally appear. The contents of the NOTICE file are for informational purposes only and do not modify the License.	You may add Your own attribution notices within Derivative Works that You distribute, alongside or as an addendum to the NOTICE text from the Work, provided that such additional attribution notices cannot be construed as modifying the License.	
The Project Gutenberg Licence	https://www.gutenberg.org/policy/license.htm#section-1-general-terms-of-use-and-redistributing-project-gutenberg-tm-electronic-works	Under permission	Under permission		

References

- Admiraal, Femmy, Scharnhorst, Andrea, Daga, Enrico, Daquino, Marilena, Musumeci, Elena, Kranenburg, Peter, Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, Gurrieri, Marco, Presutti, Valentina, Clementi, Marta, Meroño Peñuela, Albert, Turci, Monica, Marzi, Eleonora, Puglisi, Antonio, & Fournier-S'niehotta, Raphaël. (2021). D7.1 First Data Management Plan (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6963585>
- Carriero, Valentina Anita; Fiorela Ciroku, Jacopo de Berardinis, Delfinai Sol Martínez Pandiani, Albert Meroño-Peñuela, Andrea Poltronieri, & Valentina Presutti. (2022). Polifonia Ontology Network, vo.1 (vo.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6259925>
- Daga, Enrico, Meroño Peñuela, Albert, Daquino, Marilena, Ciroku, Fiorela, Musumeci, Elena, Gurrieri, Marco, Scharnhorst, Andrea, Admiraal, Femmy, & Fournier-S'niehotta, Raphaël. (2021). D1.3: Pilots development – collaborative methodology and tools (V1.0) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7124135>
- Daquino, Marilena, Meroño Peñuela, Albert, Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, & Mulholland, Paul. (2022). D1.9: Polifonia Web portal - 1st version (V1.0) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7116711>
- Diamond, Danny, Shahid, Abdul, & McDermott, James. (2022). D3.3: Software Tools for Mining Patterns in Music Repositories (V1.0) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118763>
- Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, Bottini, Thomas, Carriero, Valentina, Carvalho, Jason, Cathé, Philippe, Ciroku, Fiorela, Daga, Enrico, Daquino, Marilena, Davy-Rigaux, Achille, Gurrieri, Marco, Van Kemenade, Philo, Marzi, Eleanora, Presutti, Valentina, & Scharnhorst, Andrea. (2021). D1.1 Roadmap and pilot requirements 1st version (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7124253>
- Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, De Berardinis, Jacopo, Bottini, Thomas, Cathé, Philippe, Daga, Enrico, Daquino, Marilena, Davy-Rigaux, Achille, Gurrieri, Marco, Van Kranenburg, Peter, Marzi, Eleanora, McDermott, James, Meroño Peñuela, Albert, Mulholland, Paul, Scharnhorst, Andrea, & Tripodi, Rocco. (2022). D1.2 Roadmap and pilot requirements 2nd version (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7116561>
- Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, Gurrieri, Marco, van Kranenburg, Peter, Musumeci, Elena, Veninata, Chiara, Berardinis, Jacopo de, Fournier-S'niehotta, Raphaël, Marzi, Eleonora, Barlow, Helen, Daga, Enrico, & Holland, Simon. (2022a). Polifonia Survey (Version 19062022) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6664200>
- Meroño Peñuela, Albert, De Berardinis, Jacopo, Martinez Pandiani, Delfina Sol, Carriero, Valentina, Wigham, Mari, Poltronieri, Andrea, Ciroku, Fiorela, Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, & Rigaux, Philippe. (2021). D2.1: Ontology-based knowledge graphs for music objects (V1.0) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7134763>
- Meroño Peñuela, Albert, De Berardinis, Jacopo, Ciroku, Fiorela, Carriero, Valentina, Wigham, Mari, Daga, Enrico, Marzi, Eleanora, Musumeci, Elena, Van Kranenburg, Peter, Scharnhorst, Andrea, McDermott,

James, Rigaux, Philippe, Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, & Holland, Simon. (2022). D2.4: Methods for interlinking knowledge graphs (V1.0) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7116793>

Meroño Peñuela, Albert, De Berardinis, Jacopo, Ciroku, Fiorela, & Carriero, Valentina. (2022a). D2.7: Ontology testing and evaluation report; knowledge graph documentation and access interfaces (V1.0) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118710>

Tripodi, Rocco, Marzi, Eleanora, Graciotti, Arianna, Zotti, Valeria, Luporini, Antonella, Turci, Monica, Pano Alaman, Ana, Van Kranenburg, Peter, Van Horik, Rene, Daga, Enrico, & Daquino, Marilena. (2022). D4.2 : Interrogation and annotation of plurilingual corpora for discourse analysis (V1.0) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118778>